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Contributor(s)	
Reviewer(s)	Valerie Gaudin, Christian Duquennoi
Approved by	Rosemarie Bernabe

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5.	Partner	Oslo Metropolitan University	OsloMet	Norway
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BEYOND Best Practices Manual: a complement to the BEYOND Guidelines for Preventing and Addressing Research Misconduct

Legend

ACRONYM	MEANING
CRPs	Contestable Research Practices
ECoC	European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity
RE	Research Ethics
RFOs	Research Funding Organisations
RI	Research Integrity
RIO	Research Integrity Offices
RM	Research Misconduct
RPOs	Research Performing Organisations
GS	Guidelines Section

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Chapter 1: Introduction and Definition of Terms

Author: Rosemarie de la Cruz Bernabe, University of Oslo

1.1. Summary

The BEYOND Best Practices Manual explains the main concepts, scope, and structure of the BEYOND approach to preventing and addressing research misconduct and shows how it complements the BEYOND Guidelines for Preventing and Addressing Research Misconduct. It introduces the core terms adopted from the Guidelines, outlines the rationale for focusing on research misconduct (RM), contestable research practices (CRPs), research ethics (RE), and research integrity (RI), and guides readers on how to navigate the Manual’s subsequent chapters.

1.2. Overview and Relevance of the Chapter

The BEYOND project is grounded in an ecosystem approach (see Image) to RM, recognising that RM and CRPs arise from interactions between individual, organisational, structural, socio-technical, and psychological factors. The Best Practices Manual is situated within this ecosystem perspective and translates the high-level, aspirational BEYOND Guidelines into operational, context-sensitive practices for diverse stakeholders in the research ecosystem.

The Manual is relevant to all stakeholders addressed in the BEYOND Guidelines, including researchers at all career stages, RPOs, RFOs, citizen scientists, ethics and integrity bodies, publishers, and policymakers. As a practical companion to the Guidelines, it brings together evidence-informed analysis, recommendations, tools, and case examples that can be adapted to specific institutional, national, and disciplinary contexts.

BEYOND Ecosystem Approach: research misconduct and research integrity are shaped by interactions between individual, organizational, and structural levels.

1.3. Guideline References

The BEYOND Best Practices Manual explicitly complements and operationalises the BEYOND Guidelines for Preventing and Addressing Research Misconduct. Whereas the Guidelines present concise, principle-based and aspirational provisions, the Manual:

- Elaborates behavioural, organisational, and structural factors that shape RM and CRPs;
- Translates guideline provisions into concrete, context-sensitive practices and decision points;
- Offers implementation tips, tools, and case examples that show how guideline recommendations can be realised in practice.

1.4. Definition of Terms (as used in this Manual)

This section sets out how key terms from the BEYOND Guidelines are used within the Manual. For the full authoritative wording, readers are encouraged to consult Section 1 of the Guidelines; the Manual uses the same concepts but tailors them to its practical focus.

Research Misconduct (RM)

RM covers serious breaches such as fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism, as well as other clearly unacceptable research practices that undermine the integrity of research. In this Manual, RM is treated both as individual wrongdoing and as behaviour that is shaped by wider organisational and systemic conditions, in line with the BEYOND ecosystem approach.

Contestable Research Practices (CRPs)

CRPs are research behaviours whose ethical acceptability is not universally agreed and can depend on disciplinary, methodological, or epistemic context. They are not automatically unethical but can raise concerns about RI if used in ways that compromise transparency, rigour, or fairness; the Manual uses CRPs primarily to highlight “grey areas” where context-sensitive judgement and dialogue are needed.

Research Integrity (RI)

RI refers to the shared responsibility across the research ecosystem to conduct and support research in ways that are reliable, honest, respectful, and accountable. The Manual adopts this understanding and focuses on how environments, incentives, competencies, and communities can be shaped so that RI becomes the norm rather than the exception.

Research Ethics (RE)

RE is understood as the application of ethical theories and principles to research, especially when human participants, animals, the environment, or other sensitive subjects are involved. It provides the normative foundation for RI, and the Manual therefore treats RE and RI as closely interconnected: ethics articulates values and principles, while integrity operationalises them through rules, practices, and institutional arrangements.

Rehabilitation

Rehabilitation is a proportionate, context-sensitive process through which a researcher who has committed RM can, when appropriate, demonstrate learning, accountability, and renewed capacity for responsible research. In the Manual, rehabilitation is treated as a structured pathway that balances accountability with opportunities for re-establishing trust and contribution to the research community.

Reintegration

Reintegration refers to the process by which a researcher returns to active participation in the research community after RM-related proceedings, including tailored training, support, and conditions adapted to the specific case. The Manual uses this term mainly in connection with practical measures, such as reintegration plans and supportive organisational cultures, discussed in later chapters.

Nudges

Nudges are subtle, low-cost changes in the research environment that encourage more ethical choices without removing freedom of decision. Within the Manual, nudges are treated as part of a broader set of behavioural and organisational interventions (e.g. prompts, default options, recognition schemes) that can make responsible conduct easier and more salient in everyday research practice.

1.5. Explanation of the BEYOND Sections

The BEYOND Guidelines and the Best Practices Manual share a common conceptual architecture around causes, impacts, and responses to RM and CRPs. This chapter provides a high-level map of how the Manual's chapters align with specific guideline sections:

Chapter 2 builds on the Preamble and guideline sections on researcher well-being, research culture, handling allegations, support mechanisms, nudges, and training to analyse individual, organisational, and structural causes of RM, using the CICO framework (Competencies, Incentives, Communities, Opportunities).

Chapter 3 develops the guideline sections on socio-economic impacts and health and well-being into a more detailed analysis of how RM affects resources, institutions, communities, and public trust.

Chapter 4 operationalises sections on prevention, trust and public engagement, supportive research cultures, procedures for handling allegations, whistleblowing, and rehabilitation.

Chapter 5 elaborates sections 12–15 of the Guidelines on RERI training, pedagogy, and indicators of effectiveness.

Because Chapters 4 and 5 are strongly oriented towards implementation, this introductory chapter highlights how they can be used as practical resources.

- *For institutional leaders and practitioners*, Chapter 4 summarises key decision points, process designs, and supportive measures for preventing and addressing RM in ways consistent with the Guidelines.
- *For educators and training developers*, Chapter 5 offers examples of pedagogical approaches, evaluation strategies, and indicators of effectiveness that align with guideline provisions on training and supervision.

1.6. Structure of the Chapters in this Manual

Each chapter in the BEYOND Best Practices Manual follows a common structure so that readers can easily navigate between topics and compare approaches across different areas. While the content differs, most chapters include the following elements:

- **Summary and overview:** A short explanation of the chapter's focus, its rationale, and why it matters in the broader BEYOND ecosystem approach.
- **Guideline references:** A section that links the chapter explicitly to the relevant provisions in the BEYOND Guidelines, making clear which articles or sections are being operationalised.
- **Explanation of the BEYOND sections:** A substantive part where key concepts, challenges, and evidence are discussed.
- **Implementation tips and tools:** Actionable guidance such as examples of policies, procedures, interventions, checklists, or templates that stakeholders can adapt to their own contexts.
- **Case examples:** Real-life scenarios, vignettes, or illustrative stories that show how practices work in practice, including comments that highlight lessons learned and potential pitfalls.
- **Further reading and resources:** Suggestions for additional documents, tools, and platforms (including other BEYOND deliverables and external resources) that readers can consult for more detail.

1.7. Further Reading and Resources

For readers seeking more detail on the concepts introduced here, the main resources are:

- The [BEYOND Guidelines for Preventing and Addressing Research Misconduct](#) (especially the Preamble and Section 1 on definitions), which provide the authoritative conceptual framework and definitions that this Manual follows.
- Other BEYOND deliverables that underpin the Manual's analysis and recommendations and are cited in later chapters. These may be found in the BEYOND website:

<https://beyondbadapples.eu/> and the BEYOND Zenodo Community:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/beyondbadappleseu/>

These documents should be read alongside the [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#), which provides the broader European reference point for RI and is explicitly affirmed in the BEYOND Guidelines.

Statement on the use of Generative AI in producing Chapter 1

Chapter 1 of this Best Practices Manual was partially developed with the assistance of PerplexityPro and ChatGPT. Perplexity was used to organise existing BEYOND project content, to align the introductory chapter with the structure and terminology of the BEYOND Guidelines, and to suggest phrasing that harmonises definitions, stakeholder descriptions, and contextual explanations. In addition, ChatGPT was used to generate a conceptual diagram illustrating the BEYOND ecosystem approach, which is included in Chapter 1 as a visual aid. All substantive concepts, scope decisions, references, and final formulations are based on BEYOND materials and have been drafted, reviewed and validated by the author. Responsibility for the chapter's content and the interpretation of the BEYOND framework rests with the named author.

Chapter 2: Individual, Organizational, and Structural Causes of Research Misconduct

Authors:

Alina Coman, Oslo Metropolitan University

Tonje Lossius Husum, Oslo Metropolitan University

Keziah Chanyisa Khayadi Dash, University of Oslo

Kalypso Iordanou, University of Central Lancashire Cyprus¹

2.1. Overview and Relevance of the Chapter

This chapter provides an overview of the factors that contribute to RM and CRPs, drawing on insights from psychology, particularly moral psychology, behavioural research, and organisational studies. It shows how individual dispositions and psychological traits interact with organisational and structural conditions to shape researchers' ethical behaviour and research integrity.

The chapter further demonstrates that RI risks extend beyond publicly funded research, highlighting gaps in oversight and accountability in NGO-funded and privately sponsored research. It also identifies key limitations in existing RE/RI policies, guidelines, and training, including issues related to clarity, enforcement, and contextual relevance.

Building on the BEYOND ecosystem approach, the chapter reframes RI as a systemic concern that requires institutional commitment, structural change, and coordinated interventions across multiple levels of the research ecosystem.

2.2. Guideline References

Although the BEYOND Guidelines do not contain a dedicated section on the causes of RM, several sections implicitly reflect the multi-level factors that contribute to RM. These sections collectively support the ecosystem perspective developed in this chapter.

Preamble: Establishes the ecosystem approach, recognising that RM emerges from the interaction of systemic, organisational, epistemic, socio-technical, and psychological factors.

Section 3 (Health and Well-being of Researchers): Highlights how workplace conditions, inequality, and psychological stressors influence researcher behaviour and vulnerability to RM.

¹ Author contribution statement: All authors contributed significantly to the development and completion of this chapter. Alina Coman and Tonje Lossius Husum outlined the thematic disposition of the chapter, and the four authors contributed by writing a part of the chapter each. Alina Coman and Tonje Lossius Husum revised the last version, and all four authors have approved the final version for publication.

Section 5 (Fostering a Supportive and Responsible Research Culture): Addresses the role of institutional culture, incentive structures (e.g., publish-or-perish), and leadership in shaping research practices.

Section 6 (Handling RM Allegations): Emphasises the importance of context-sensitive assessment, including disciplinary norms and systemic contributing factors.

Section 8 (Support and Learning Mechanisms): Recognises RM as an opportunity for institutional learning, including identifying underlying causes and systemic weaknesses.

Section 10 (Whistleblowing and Protection): Reflects the role of power dynamics, fear of retaliation, and organisational climate in enabling or suppressing reporting.

Section 11 (Nudges): Explicitly draws on behavioural insights, including psychological and environmental factors influencing ethical decision-making.

Section 12–13 (RE/RI Training and Supervision): Highlights the role of training, mentoring, and career-stage differences in shaping research behaviour.

For whom is this chapter: This chapter is relevant to all stakeholders involved in or supporting research, including researchers, RPOs, RFOs, policymakers, and those responsible for RE/RI policies and training. It is particularly useful for those seeking to understand the factors that contribute to RM and CRPs and how these arise across individual, organisational, and structural levels of the research ecosystem.

2.3. Explanation of the BEYOND Sections

This chapter expands on the evidence for behavioural, organisational, and structural factors that influence RM. The ethos of BEYOND is to offer an ecosystemic framework; thus, behavioural causes and changes must not be understood in isolation from institutional and structural conditions. Explaining RM exclusively in terms of personality traits risks essentialising behaviour and reducing it to individual factors. While this may apply in some cases, it is relevant only for a minority of cases.

To capture this complexity, BEYOND proposes a framework that identifies four broad categories of causes of problematic research behaviours, alongside four corresponding intervention levers: *competencies, incentives, communities, and opportunities* (CICO framework). These dimensions cut across individual, organisational, and structural levels, allowing both diagnosis of causes and identification of points for intervention.

2.3.1. Individual Factors

Research from moral and behavioural psychology shows that RM is associated with an interaction between competitive research environments and individual dispositions. These include ethical orientations such as consequentialism (prioritising outcomes over process), as well as traits such as manipulation, amorality, psychopathy¹, low conscientiousness, low self-control, negative emotionality, poor self-efficacy, impulsivity (though further evidence is needed), and attitudes that treat rules as flexible. Additional correlates include low agreeableness, negative attitudes toward ethics, low intrinsic motivation, and limited

creativity. Social psychological mechanisms—such as conformity, reciprocity norms, role schemata, and status—also shape behaviour².

From a CICO perspective, these factors relate primarily to competencies, understood not only as skills but also as capacities for ethical reasoning, self-regulation, and judgement.

Self-regulation: Some CRPs (e.g., p-hacking, selective analysis) resemble habitual behaviours and involve similar self-regulatory challenges. Sustained adherence to RI may therefore depend on explicit goal setting and strategies to resist situational pressures.

Goal orientations: Researchers driven by appearance goals—seeking to demonstrate competence rather than advance knowledge—are more likely to engage in CRPs, as they prioritise outcomes over rigour^{1,2}.

Virtues and epistemic vices: The absence of virtues (e.g., honesty) and the presence of epistemic vices (e.g., tendencies toward deception) weaken commitment to truthfulness and methodological rigour, creating predispositions toward RM³.

2.3.2. Organisational and Structural Factors

Individuals operate within institutional environments that shape behaviour through norms, expectations, and social influence. Laboratory and institutional climates can either promote integrity or normalise CRPs^{4,5}. Leadership, peer behaviour, and broader societal values all contribute to shaping research practices.

Within the CICO framework, these factors map primarily onto:

- Incentives (what is rewarded or penalised)
- Communities (norms, cultures, and social relations)
- Opportunities (structural conditions enabling or constraining behaviour)

2.3.2.1 Incentives: Financial and publication pressures

Institutional reward systems that prioritise quantitative metrics over research quality create strong incentives for CRPs. “Publish or perish” cultures—especially when reinforced by funding, promotion criteria, or financial rewards—encourage prioritisation of output over rigour^{6,8}.

When transparency and methodological quality are not adequately rewarded, CRPs may be perceived as necessary for career survival. High productivity demands, combined with expectations of constant availability, create high-pressure environments marked by stress, isolation, and reduced well-being, reinforcing outcome-oriented behaviour⁹.

Conflicts of interest, external pressures, stakeholder loyalties, and politicisation of research further distort incentives and may increase RM risks. In some cases, institutions may mismanage or even conceal RM to protect reputational or financial interests. Increasing politicisation of research ethics debates also affects public trust in science¹⁰.

2.3.2.2. Organisational cultures and communities

Institutional and disciplinary cultures shape norms of acceptable behaviour. When institutions or journals prioritise reputation over integrity, reporting of RM may be discouraged⁴. Legal frameworks that expose whistleblowers to risk further suppress reporting¹¹.

Power imbalances, discrimination, harassment, and exploitation create environments in which individuals may feel unable to challenge problematic practices. These dynamics can normalise silence and increase RM risks, particularly in sensitive research areas.

Gender is frequently present in RM case descriptions, but evidence does not support gender as a general predictor of RM¹². Rather, gender-related factors operate through broader structural inequalities, including discrimination, stereotyping, and intersectionality.

Recent developments show a shift from focusing on researchers' gender to examining how gendered research topics themselves become ethically contested. Cases of research projects involving topics of sexuality, fertility, or gender dysphoria illustrate how evolving social norms intersect with RE/RI concerns, requiring context-sensitive ethical reflection (see cases page 17).

2.3.2.3. Guidelines, definitions, and policies: Opportunities

The effectiveness of RE/RI policies remains uneven. Weak enforcement mechanisms, unclear sanctions, and ambiguous definitions of CRPs reduce deterrence and accountability^{13,14}. Complex or inconsistent rules may even incentivise researchers to cut corners¹⁵.

CRPs are inherently difficult to define due to their context-dependent and ethically ambiguous nature¹⁶. Practices such as HARKing, selective reporting, or gift authorship often fall within disciplinary “grey areas,” making their evaluation dependent on norms and context¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

Gaps in governance are particularly evident in but not limited to:

- journal policies and international standards
- emerging technologies (e.g. AI)
- NGO and privately funded research, which often lack oversight.

These gaps create opportunities—in the CICO sense—for RM to occur due to insufficient regulation, accountability, or clarity.

2.3.2.4. Training and Education

RE/RI training is a key intervention area within the CICO framework, particularly affecting competencies, but also shaping communities and opportunities.

Inadequate training—especially when overly theoretical, passive, or compliance-focused—fails to prepare researchers to recognise and address ethical challenges. Many contexts also lack support structures such as ethics advisors or statistical consultants.

A major limitation is the lack of attention to specific CRPs. General principles alone are insufficient; understanding practices such as p-hacking or HARKing requires detailed, context-

sensitive knowledge¹⁶. Training that ignores disciplinary variation or ethical “grey areas” fails to equip researchers for real-world decision-making²⁰.

Training effectiveness is further limited by:

- lack of adaptation to career stages (with early-career researchers at higher risk)¹⁶
- uneven engagement across disciplines
- reliance on passive teaching methods.

Active, practice-based approaches—such as case discussions and interactive learning—are more effective²⁰. Moderate realism and emotional engagement enhance learning outcomes.

Another key gap is the separation between formal and informal learning. Mentoring, peer interaction, and ongoing dialogue are essential for reinforcing ethical behaviour²¹. Outdated materials and lack of regular updates further weaken training relevance.

Training is also less effective when delivered by instructors lacking scientific credibility. Compliance-oriented approaches that focus on rules rather than reasoning fail to prepare researchers for complex ethical situations. Reflexive approaches that develop ethical judgement are more effective^{21, 22}.

Finally, early-career researchers are particularly influenced by their supervisors. Mentoring relationships play a crucial role in shaping behaviour, with evidence showing that researchers are more likely to engage in CRPs when their mentors do^{23, 24}. This highlights the importance of leadership, incentives, and research culture in shaping conduct².

2.4. Case Example(s)

Case 1 Example of how leadership, hierarchical structures, and performance expectations interact and can shape research behaviour

In a lab case, the senior academic responsible for running the lab where multiple instances of RM were identified was found to have been “reckless in the conduct of his laboratory” by the university’s investigatory panel, which also determined that his co-authorship on a number of papers, including those using fabricated data “facilitated misconduct”²⁵. Furthermore, a mid-career researcher in the lab responsible for falsifying information in publication figures on papers in which the head of the lab was a co-author had attempted to pass the blame for misconduct down the academic hierarchy to junior researchers²⁶.

Comments to the case

This case illustrates how leadership, hierarchical structures, and performance expectations interact, pointing to the role of communities and incentives (CICO) in shaping research behaviour. Attention should be given to senior researchers who face high demands related to conducting high-end research, administration, securing funding, and supervising/overseeing large teams. Such conditions may weaken oversight and diffuse responsibility, particularly in large research groups.

These dynamics reflect weaknesses in both communities (e.g., lack of trust, power imbalances) and opportunities (e.g., insufficient or ineffective reporting systems) within the CICO framework.

Lack of policies and institutional mechanisms to tackle RM²⁸, especially in low-middle income countries (LMICs), including specific offices to investigate suspected misconduct and policies to deal with scientific dishonesty²⁹, or lack of transparent reporting on cases of RM^{30,31} due to a dearth of established reporting mechanisms for discovering and monitoring RM incidents can hinder prevention or research of causes and patterns of RM^{6,32}.

These structural gaps further illustrate how limited institutional capacity creates opportunities (CICO) for RM to occur or persist.

Case 2 Example of how weak oversight and delayed detection can let RM persist

A researcher was accused of fraud in multiple cases. This case highlights the potential harms that can occur when RM goes undetected, or when reporting is delayed or the investigation is protracted over multiple years. In addition to these matters, the researcher in question was suspected of tampering with grant applications and removing other authors' names from reports³³.

Comments to the case

This case demonstrates that when the perceived likelihood of detection is low, opportunities for RM increase.

Research has also shown that researchers' perception of the likelihood of being 'caught' misbehaving or engaging in questionable behaviour reduces the likelihood of such misbehaviour^{34,35}.

Case 3 A case that demonstrates how supervision failure and unclear responsibility boundaries can lead to RM

In this case, a research team published an article in Nature claiming to have experimentally observed Majorana particles – theoretical particles that are not charged and have no mass – which can be significant in the development of quantum computers. However, the article's conclusions were subsequently demonstrated to be incorrect and irreproducible. The journal officially retracted the article on the grounds of errors in the data analysis³⁶, and another article involving the same authors was also retracted³⁷.

The investigation found the researchers to have been “negligent” and to have breached three basic principles of the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity³⁸: ‘honesty and scrupulousness’, ‘transparency’, and ‘responsibility,’ but found that they had not deliberately committed RM.

The investigation placed primary responsibility on the first author, who was a doctoral student, but also determined that a senior researcher who was both the corresponding author for the paper and the first author's PhD supervisor bore “full responsibility.” The RI board's findings further recommended that the university articulate clear guidelines and document agreements to enable research supervisors to fulfil their responsibilities effectively and, when necessary,

be held accountable. This approach is intended to eliminate ambiguity regarding the degree to which senior researchers are ultimately responsible for the actions of junior researchers under their supervision³⁹.

Comment to the case

This case highlights the interaction between competencies and communities (CICO), particularly the role of supervision, mentoring, and clarity of responsibilities in shaping research conduct.

Another factor correlated with delays in reporting is an RPO mitigating or covering up whistleblower allegations of RM to protect the institution from reputational damage. While this was evidenced in only one case in this review, the ramifications for RE/RI and public trust in science are significant.

Case 4 Example of how organisational cultures and structural conditions can suppress reporting and allow misconduct to persist

A university found that researchers from a lab run by a prominent professor published fraudulent papers with manipulated and falsified data over a number of years. Investigations found that the professor in charge of the lab was responsible for RM because he managed his lab recklessly and listed himself as a co-author on fraudulent publications, although the reports note that his actions may not have been intentional⁴⁰.

However, media investigations also uncovered an e-mail between administrators that showed that the university had hushed up whistle-blower complaints and avoided investigating the professor's lab in order to protect against reputational damage to the university²⁶.

Comments to the case

This case illustrates how institutional priorities and reputational concerns can shape responses to RM, pointing to the role of communities and opportunities (CICO).

Several cases have highlighted instances where prominent research institutions did not adequately support whistle-blowers, and at times even fostered an inhospitable environment for them. Mechanisms for reporting and protecting whistle-blowers were found to be insufficiently robust and lacking in formality, sometimes resulting in inadequate responses to instances of RM. In certain situations, institutional interests may inadvertently discourage addressing such cases.

These patterns reinforce how organisational cultures and structural conditions can suppress reporting and allow misconduct to persist.

Nevertheless, this study also identified exemplary cases in which institutions effectively supported whistle-blowers and undertook thorough and conscientious investigations into their claims.

2.5. Summary

- This chapter shows that RM and CRPs are rarely just the result of “bad apples”; they emerge from the interaction of individual dispositions with organisational cultures, incentive structures, and broader systemic conditions. It argues that pressures, norms, power relations, and policy gaps across the research ecosystem can collectively create environments in which RM and CRPs become more likely, especially when accountability, support, and oversight are weak.
- The chapter uses the CICO framework—Competencies, Incentives, Communities, and Opportunities—as a way to make sense of these multi-level influences, helping stakeholders diagnose how systemic conditions shape behaviour. Overall, it reframes RI as a shared, system-level responsibility that depends on institutional commitment and coordinated interventions, using CICO as a practical lens for designing and aligning these interventions.

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Chapter 3: Impacts of Research Misconduct

Authors²³

Vivian Nchanchou Mbanya, University of Oslo
Pooja Aryal, University of Oslo
Ian Slesinger, Trilateral Research
Rosemarie de La Cruz Bernabe, University of Oslo

3.1. Overview and Relevance of the Chapter

Instances of RM are not just personal ethical failures but often involve multiple structural and contextual factors that contribute to their occurrence, as well as their impacts. These impacts can result in negative consequences that undermine the scientific enterprise, cause economic damage and hinder innovation, and lead to societal harm. RM impacts come in a diversity of forms and at different magnitudes and lead to a range of effects on different aspects of social and economic life. Both private- and public-sector stakeholders are affected by RM. RM does not only affect RFOs, RPOs, researchers and students; it affects administrators, authors, publishers, academic institutions, educators, research collaborators, public health bodies, policymakers, research participants, medical/paramedical professionals, patients and their relatives, perpetrators, the scientific community, and society. Depending on the context and their involvement, those affected by RM may experience either direct or indirect consequences. This chapter aims to provide concrete context as well as the key points for the most relevant aspects of the impacts of RM on the research ecosystem, economy, policy, and society. This section focuses on research in general, not on one research sector.

3.2. Guideline References

The impacts of RM analysed in this chapter are directly reflected across several sections of the BEYOND Guidelines, which address the consequences of RM for researchers, institutions, and society, and propose corresponding responses.

Section 2 (Addressing the Socio-economic Impacts of RM): Highlights the broad consequences of RM for scientific progress, innovation, funding, public trust, and the wider research ecosystem, including economic and societal implications.

² Author contribution statement: All authors contributed significantly to the development and completion of this chapter. Rosemarie de La Cruz Bernabe conceived the chapter's core thematic framework and oversaw the final structural and content revisions. Vivian Nchanchou Mbanya drafted the initial section and led the subsequent text revisions. Rosemarie de La Cruz Bernabe, Vivian Nchanchou Mbanya, Pooja Aryal, and Ian Slesinger critically reviewed, edited, and approved the final version for publication.

Section 3 (Health and Well-being of Researchers): Addresses the effects of RM-related environments on researchers' well-being, including stress, inequality, and unsafe working conditions, and emphasises the importance of supportive and inclusive research environments.

Section 4 (Establishing Trust: Public Engagement and Institutional Foundations): Focuses on the relationship between RM, public trust, and science communication, highlighting the need for transparency and proactive engagement to maintain trust in science.

Section 5 (Fostering a Supportive and Responsible Research Culture): Links research culture and incentive structures to both the occurrence and consequences of RM, including their effects on integrity, behaviour, and institutional trust.

Section 8 (Support and Learning Mechanisms): Emphasises RM as a source of institutional learning, including the identification of systemic weaknesses and opportunities to improve research environments.

Section 9 (Rehabilitation and Reintegration of Researchers after RM): Addresses the longer-term consequences of RM for individuals and institutions, including issues of trust, accountability, and reintegration into the research community.

Section 10 (Whistleblowing and Whistleblower Protection): Reflects the personal and professional risks faced by whistleblowers and the importance of protective mechanisms to mitigate the negative consequences of reporting RM.

For whom is this chapter: This chapter is relevant to all stakeholders involved in or affected by research, including researchers, RPOs, RFOs, policymakers, publishers, and the wider public. It is particularly useful for those responsible for designing, implementing, or evaluating policies and practices related to RE/RI, as well as those seeking to understand the broader consequences of RM across different sectors.

3.3. Explanation of the BEYOND Sections

3.3.1. Socio-economic impact

3.3.1.1. Wasted Resources, Time and Efforts

Research and grant fraud can inflict considerable reputational and financial harm on institutions, affecting a wide range of stakeholders across various sectors. Specifically, RM has significant economic implications for RPOs and RFOs. When cases of RM arise, different stakeholders are required to dedicate extra effort and resources to managing and responding to them. Furthermore, researchers/research teams subjected to investigations incur substantial loss of time and effort. RM cases generate both direct and indirect costs, for example when inconsistent or unusable data have to be discarded and when institutions have to investigate allegations and manage misleading reports. The resources spent on these investigations and follow-up actions can strain already limited institutional budgets, diverting funds from education and productive research activities¹⁻³. Time, effort, and financial resources used in the investigation of allegations of RM, such as legal fees and staff payments,

represent resources that could otherwise be directed toward productive research or other institutional priorities. When RPOs invest in preventing the recurrence of RM in response to such cases, these additional prevention costs can further deplete academic budgets and/or incur financial losses or divert funds from other institutional priorities⁴ and thereby compound these opportunity costs over time.

Fabricating or falsifying data wastes researchers' time and effort and produces unusable, potentially misleading findings^{5,6}. Funds invested in such research do not only fail to generate valid knowledge but also tend to reduce available institutional and public funding and limit resources for future high-quality research.

When students engage in RM, institutions may suspend them from study programmes, exclude them from ongoing research projects, and even revoke their diplomas. The time supervisors and collaborators invested in training, supervision, and collaboration is effectively lost, as are resources allocated to data collection, management, and manuscript preparation. Research outputs and materials produced by the student can become unusable, forcing repetition of work, reallocation of funds, and delays to the wider project⁷. If the project was based on experimental studies, supervisors and team members may be required to re-run experiments, re-collect data, and redo analyses. When fraudulent data are used as evidence, they produce misleading conclusions, which divert investment and delay innovation from genuinely promising projects. Further, work that builds on fraudulent publications can harm collaborators and previous collaborators, generate social stigma, and is associated with lower citation rates and other negative publication outcomes⁸. Research built on fabricated, falsified, or questionable data wastes considerable financial and human resources, as other researchers may expend efforts trying to replicate or build upon flawed results, which hinders genuine scientific progress.

3.3.1.2. Impact on Businesses and Investments

The socioeconomic consequences of RM also extend to businesses, influencing research progress and investment decisions. RM can lead to substantial economic and reputational harm for businesses and investors, especially in industries that depend heavily on scientific research, such as pharmaceuticals, biotechnology, and technology⁹. RPOs and businesses rely on trustworthy research outputs to make informed decisions. Companies that finance or depend on fraudulent research can incur considerable financial losses¹⁰. These losses include not only wasted research and development funds but also the significant expenses associated with internal investigations, legal fees, and potential civil litigation. According to some experts, a single investigation into misconduct can cost very large sums, including hundreds of thousands or even millions of dollars and pounds^{4,9} and corporations have, in some cases, been compelled to pay millions in settlements.

A prominent example is the Mediator (benfluorex) pharmaceutical scandal involving the French company Servier and the drug Mediator, which was linked to serious heart-valve damage and deaths. After lengthy investigations and a criminal trial, Servier and several co-defendants were held legally accountable for misconduct relating to the drug's marketing and safety reporting. Unsal and Hippler showed that corporate misconduct reduces the future innovative capacity of pharmaceutical firms: after misconduct, such firms may experience fewer FDA approvals and patents, diminished reputations, fewer business partnerships,

substantial negative cumulative abnormal returns, and increased analyst concern¹¹. Existing evidence also indicates that the impact of RM goes beyond business finances and investments, affecting the professionals involved and increasing the costs of remediating misconduct. Such malpractice can damage a company's brand credibility and reputation, harm patients, undermine the safety or perceived quality of its products or technology, or even lead to the abandonment of projects, resulting in wasted time, effort, resources, and lawsuits. These risks are particularly salient for pharmaceutical and medical device companies^{12,13}.

3.3.1.3. Challenge for the Academic Community and Publishers

The impact of RM on academic institutions and publishing is significant across research fields and scientific publications. This is particularly evident in medicine, pharmaceutical research, and other biomedical disciplines. When RM occurs, it threatens research and research integrity within the scientific community. RM in academic institutions can have cascading effects: when RM is committed by an individual or research group, it not only tarnishes their reputation but also damages the reputation and standing of the institution where the research was carried out^{12,16,17}. RM can adversely affect the scientific image and visibility of the field of study and its associated community. It can impair the ability to reproduce and replicate studies in line with scientific principles and further erode public trust in the scientific community¹⁸.

Research misconduct within a scientific institution can distort and damage its reputation and research record, which may lead to reduced funding, fewer research collaboration opportunities, and weakened public and private partnerships^{4,7,19}. Such situations can provoke disagreements and conflict within research teams and result in financial repercussions, including the loss of grants, other funding, and exposure to legal liabilities. A well-known example is the case of Paolo Macchiarini²⁰, involving experimental synthetic trachea transplants and the reporting of outcomes. Investigations found serious ethical and scientific failings, including misrepresentation of patient outcomes and inadequate ethical approvals. The incidents led to professional sanctions, institutional inquiries, and major reputational damage to Karolinska Institutet, Sweden²⁰.

When a researcher in an academic institution is found to have committed RM, their credibility and professional standing can be severely affected, leading to stigma⁸. A researcher's reputation relies on trust and credibility, and once that trust is breached, it is extremely difficult to restore. Such individuals may be ostracized by colleagues and face lost opportunities for collaboration, peer review activities, research grants, and academic positions¹². The process of being investigated for RM can be emotionally and psychologically taxing. Public scrutiny, humiliation, and professional ruin can lead to significant personal and family distress and a decline in research productivity³. If the research was supported by public or private grants, both the individual and their institution may need to return funds. Legal expenses can also be significant if RM is classified as criminal, particularly in cases involving publicly funded research. In serious cases, especially those involving fraudulent data that may jeopardize public health or safety, a researcher may face criminal charges, fines, and imprisonment^{8,21}.

RM also imposes significant burdens on publishers. Confirmed cases can lead to article retractions and create financial and administrative costs related to investigations, corrections, and public notices. Retractions may reduce a journal's output and harm its reputation and impact metrics. In addition, manuscripts under investigation often experience delays in peer

review and publication, which undermines the efficiency of the publishing workflow and poses risks to the integrity of the scholarly record for both publishers and authors³. Studies have found that co-authors who worked with researchers later determined to have committed RM frequently experience marked reductions in their subsequent publication output and citation impact¹⁹.

3.3.2. Impact on health and well-being

3.3.2.1. Impact on Communities and Public Health

RM can have serious and long-lasting effects on communities and public health^{14,20,23}. Governments and policymakers rely on robust, ethical research to guide decision-making, so when flawed evidence informs policies or clinical practice, the consequences can be severe^{3,14,23}.

The health impact of RM is multifaceted, and scientific misconduct in medical research can cause very serious harm to both individual patients and public health^{14,20,23}. Although RM may appear to concern mainly researchers, journals, and institutions, it can have far-reaching consequences for communities and health systems when flawed evidence informs decisions^{14,23}. When ambition or financial gain is prioritised and patients are disregarded, companies or research teams may endanger patients' lives by relying on inaccurate empirical evidence, unverified observations, or altered research data^{14,23}. Such practices can jeopardise patient safety and community health, particularly where regulatory or professional oversight is weak¹⁴.

Threats to public health may also stem from insufficient oversight of pharmaceutical manufacturers and physician organisations¹⁴. For example, a study by Rhee and Rho linked 2014–2016 Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services Part D prescribing data with Open Payments data and found that manufacturers of three branded gabapentinoids provided approximately 11.5 million USD in payments (including gifts, educational support, and travel expenses) to 14.4% of prescribing physicians, despite known safety concerns²². Studies have also demonstrated links between unethical practices, risks to children's lives, and broader threats to public health^{20,23}.

The impact of RM on health and well-being extends beyond physical harms. RM can impose substantial psychological burdens on those who commit it, those who report or investigate it, and those affected by its consequences^{13,24–26} (see also Chapter 2). Empirical studies indicate that involvement in or exposure to RM is associated with feelings of guilt, harassment, public criticism, and distrust in science^{24,25}. Pressures to publish, unsupportive research environments, and structural, sociological, and psychological factors can undermine honesty and integrity, contributing both to RM and to adverse mental health outcomes among researchers^{24–26}. Prior work has documented substantial stigma, isolation, and feelings of betrayal among individuals not directly responsible for RM, including prior collaborators and whistleblowers^{24,25}. High levels of research-related stress, performance pressure, and fear of failure are strongly correlated with both an increased risk of engaging in RM and poorer mental health; in extreme cases, RM has been linked to suicidal behaviour^{13,26}.

3.3.2.2. Consequences for Students

When a student is involved in RM, the consequences can be substantial and multifaceted¹². If a thesis or published work is found to contain fabricated or falsified data, the document may be formally retracted from the academic record¹². The student may face disciplinary sanctions, including suspension or expulsion from the university, loss of funding or degree status, and long-term damage to their academic and professional reputation¹². Such misconduct can also result in loss of eligibility for future funding and may severely hinder or terminate an academic career, making it more difficult to gain admission to graduate programmes, secure employment, or establish a professional trajectory in research or related fields¹².

3.3.2.3. Impact on Researchers from Underrepresented Groups

The negative effects of RM are often compounded for individuals from marginalised or underrepresented groups, including women, gender-diverse researchers, and racial and ethnic minorities^{16,27–29}. These groups may be disproportionately harmed by RM due to pre-existing systemic inequalities, histories of exploitation in research, and limited institutional support^{16,27–29}. Evidence suggests that professionals from racial and ethnic minorities can face disproportionately harsh sanctions for similar acts of RM compared with majority-group peers, a pattern also reported in academic and research settings^{27–29}. The intersection of race, gender, and other minority statuses can amplify these ramifications^{27–29}.

Power and perception play a central role. As highlighted by Booker (2022), Black women who raise concerns or blow the whistle are sometimes dismissed or labelled “angry” or “confrontational”, while white women in similar situations may be framed as “courageous” or “truth tellers”²⁷. Gender norms and caregiving expectations can also influence risk perceptions: women may be acutely aware of the potential disproportionate consequences of reporting RM, contributing to gender-based under-reporting²⁸. Gender-diverse researchers may find that their gender identity is weaponised to delegitimise their professional credibility and actions as whistleblowers^{28,29}. Public reactions to whistleblowing by Daniel Ellsberg, a cisgender man, and Chelsea Manning, a transgender woman, illustrate how identity can shape how similar acts are perceived and sanctioned²⁸.

Stigma arising from an RM investigation or even a false allegation can impose a more severe burden on marginalised researchers^{27–29}. This “taint” can obstruct access to grant funding, publication opportunities, and career advancement^{27–29}. Marginalised researchers, who are often in temporary, junior, or less secure positions, may feel the burden of RM investigations more heavily because they have less social capital or fewer protective networks than senior, non-marginalised colleagues^{16,27–29}. As a result, they may be less inclined to report RM due to concerns about retaliation and long-term career harm^{16,28,29}. These gender- and identity-based disparities, combined with discrimination and harassment, can intensify the psychological toll of RM and undermine both well-being and fairness within the research environment^{16,27–29}.

3.3.2.4. Impact on Non-tenured Researchers

Researchers in temporary, precarious, or lower-status positions face heightened risks in relation to RM^{16,25–27,30–32}. They may be more susceptible to pressures to conform to unethical norms, less likely to report suspected RM, and more vulnerable to career setbacks and psychological harm when RM occurs^{16,25–27}. Their temporary status and dependence on

principal investigators or supervisors for recommendations, funding, and contract renewals increases their vulnerability to such pressure^{16,30–32}.

High-quality studies on non-tenured researchers' perceptions of working conditions and RM indicate that limited peer and supervisor support, high work demands, and unclear role definitions raise stress levels³⁰. These studies also show that stress, low job satisfaction, and related organisational factors are significantly associated with a greater likelihood of behaviours that violate ethical research principles³⁰. This pressure is particularly pronounced for early-career researchers with limited job security, making them a high-risk group for both involvement in and victimisation by RM^{25–27,30}. Because junior researchers often learn ethical norms from their supervisors, weak supervisory standards and problematic role-modelling can normalise RM and CRPs^{16,30–32}.

Recent research increasingly points to job insecurity and career prospects as important determinants of psycho-physical well-being and of work practices more generally^{30,43,44}. At the same time, evidence suggests that RM is driven more by adverse socio-organisational factors (such as incentive structures, leadership, and culture) than by non-tenured researchers' individual vulnerabilities alone^{16,30}. Exposure to RM during training or mentorship can negatively affect the development of future researchers, perpetuating problematic norms across generations^{8,24,25}. It can shatter trust in institutions and colleagues, producing profound disillusionment, cynicism, and a sense of betrayal^{8,24,25}. The stress of working in an unethical environment, or the fear of retaliation for reporting RM, can lead to psychological distress, including stigma, chronic anxiety, and depression^{8,24}. A researcher's reputation may be unjustly damaged simply through association with a project or colleague linked to RM, regardless of their actual involvement, and a hostile work environment can obstruct professional development, networking, and future opportunities^{2,19}.

3.3.2.5. Impact on Whistleblowers

For potential whistleblowers, the primary consideration in deciding whether to report RM is often an assessment of personal risk^{33,34}. These risks may include termination, demotion, harassment, or isolation in the workplace, as well as damage to public and professional reputation^{33,34}. Theoretical and empirical work shows that power dynamics strongly influence whether alleged RM is reported, with academic seniority, employment status (permanent versus temporary), and gender shaping reporting decisions^{16,35}. Similar power factors have been identified as key drivers of organisational integrity in studies of commercial organisations^{16,35}.

Fear of workplace retaliation, including job loss, employer-initiated legal action, harassment, and subtle forms of exclusion—along with gender-based discrimination, social stigmatisation, perceptions of wrongdoing seriousness, lack of support, and scepticism about institutional responses, all deter individuals from reporting RM^{28,36–38}. Documented cases of retaliation against whistleblowers highlight the impact of institutional power dynamics, which often intersect with gender, race, and other axes of marginalisation, making it especially difficult for vulnerable individuals to speak up without facing severe personal and professional consequences^{16,28,38}. Intersecting forms of oppression related to sexual orientation, gender identity, race, educational background, and age shape whistleblowers' experiences; female

whistleblowers in particular may face distinct challenges in how they are publicly perceived and in the repercussions they encounter²⁷⁻²⁹.

Retaliation against whistleblowers can cause lasting mental-health and reputational harm, sometimes removing them from the workforce and increasing long-term dependence on public assistance³⁹. Such environments foster helplessness and exacerbate psychological distress, creating conditions in which RM can go unchecked because individuals are discouraged from reporting concerns^{16,38,39}.

3.3.2.6. Career and Reputation Damage

Beyond the legal consequences of RM, it can cause profound professional and reputational damage and, in some cases, serious public harm. A notable example is Andrew Wakefield's 1998 paper in *The Lancet*, which relied on falsified data to claim an association between the measles, mumps, and rubella (MMR) vaccine and autism²³. The article was subsequently retracted, and Wakefield was barred from practising medicine in the UK²³. Although later investigations and numerous studies found no evidence of a link between the MMR vaccine and autism, the social damage had already been done; public fear increased, vaccination rates declined, and measles, previously under control in some regions, resurged, contributing to outbreaks and deaths and helping fuel an anti-vaccine movement that placed more children at risk²³.

RM undermines the reputation of researchers, RPOs, and entire disciplines^{8,11,17,39}. Notable incidents of RM can severely undermine public trust in scientific organisations and in international bodies that rely on scientific evidence⁴⁰⁻⁴². The consequences of RM are often intensified for individuals. People wrongly implicated in RM may experience lasting harm to their well-being and standing within the research community, manifesting as professional isolation, demotion, and career stagnation¹⁹. Some studies have demonstrated that work-related stressors and perceived dysfunctions in the working environment are key predictors of various health outcomes, including psychological distress^{43,44}.

Researchers found to have committed RM suffer significant reputational damage, leading to a loss of trust from peers and the wider scientific community^{12,34}. RM can also result in reputational damage for the institutions employing the authors and for the journals that publish the compromised work⁴. It undermines the development of a healthy, inclusive, and respectful research culture, as loss of trust, heightened fear, problematic power dynamics, reduced collegiality, increased social risks, and diminished psychological safety make the research environment less supportive and more hostile for everyone⁴⁵. When misconduct is tolerated or inadequately addressed, psychological safety erodes and people are discouraged from speaking up; consequently, individuals may remain silent or leave the field altogether, further perpetuating this negative culture^{1,45}.

3.3.3. Impact on Public Trust and Trustworthiness of Science

3.3.3.1. Impact on the Broader Research Community

The consequences of RM extend beyond individual institutions to the scientific community as a whole. RM threatens the foundational role of science as a trustworthy source of knowledge

and a pillar of democratic societies^{16,34,46}. Oreskes argues that public trust in science is not based on personal verification of every fact but on confidence in the integrity and reliability of the scientific process itself⁴⁶. Science is a collective, self-correcting enterprise; when this system is corrupted by RM, it becomes harder for the public to distinguish between sound evidence and fraudulent claims^{41,42,46}.

Revelations of RM can lead to widespread scepticism about the reliability and objectivity of scientific research, diminishing the public's willingness to accept scientific advice or support research initiatives^{20,47}. RM significantly erodes trust in research by compromising the reliability and transparency of findings, leading to diminished confidence among researchers, policymakers, and the public^{1,41,42}. Practices such as p-hacking, HARKing, and selective reporting can result in false positives or exaggerated outcomes, which misguide future research efforts and divert funding and effort down unproductive paths^{41,42}. Even where behaviour does not meet formal thresholds for RM, researchers identified as engaging in these practices may experience damage to their professional reputation and strained collaborations^{12,34}.

A research environment where RM or contestable practices are prevalent fosters a toxic culture, driven by pressures to publish, intense competition, and inadequate training, and may create a dysfunctional and unsustainable research system^{16,34}. Additionally, unfair authorship practices, including honorary, gift, or ghost authorship, distort the fair allocation of credit and lead to disputes that undermine collaborative trust^{1,41,42}. Lack of transparency makes it difficult or impossible to reproduce findings, directly impeding the self-correcting nature of science and slowing progress^{1,41,42}. Research based on fraudulent data wastes significant financial and human resources that could have been allocated to legitimate studies, delaying genuine scientific progress and, in applied fields such as medicine, potentially contributing to harmful treatments or policies^{1,41,42}.

Decreasing public trust in science can also lead to a decline in volunteer participation in scientific studies, impacting the feasibility and quality of future research^{1,20,47}. RM involving breaches of data protection or confidentiality can further influence potential participants' decisions, particularly in social and behavioural sciences and pharmaceutical research, thereby eroding public trust and threatening the credibility of research^{1,41,42}.

3.3.3.2. Misconduct in Science and Public Mistrust

The effects of RM on trust are often long-lasting and difficult to repair^{19,24,47}. RM compromises the integrity of peer-review processes and diminishes the trustworthiness of academic publications, making it harder for readers to assess the quality of evidence. It can foster mistrust among research collaborators and make research participants more hesitant to engage in studies, resulting in a broader reluctance to participate in scientific endeavours^{19,24}. As a consequence, RPOs face reputational damage, increased liability risks, and heightened mistrust from the public^{4,7,19}. Researchers and students associated with RM risk jeopardising their careers, even when they are not directly responsible, further compounding the decline in public trust in science and confidence in the scientific community^{19,24}.

This erosion of confidence has significant implications, particularly for students and early-career researchers who may rely on flawed research or data and may be inadvertently associated with RM offenders^{19,24}. Collectively, the scientific community can suffer from diminished trust, reduced perceived relevance, and potential funding withdrawals, as well as weakened relationships with policymakers, funders, and the public that can hinder future studies^{20,47,51}. This erosion of confidence can directly affect the public's willingness to accept scientific guidance on critical issues such as health, climate change, and public policy^{20,47,51}.

Several high-profile cases illustrate how academic fraud and serious misconduct can trigger crises of confidence. For example, image manipulation allegations in research associated with senior leadership at Stanford University contributed to campus-wide instability and the resignation of the university president⁴⁷. Another striking case is the Paolo Macchiarini trachea scandal at Karolinska Institutet, in which fraudulent medical research on artificial tracheas led to patient deaths and revealed serious failures in institutional oversight; the initial protection of the researcher by the institution contributed to a major loss of public trust in both the university and the broader academic system²⁰.

3.3.3.3. AI RM and Trust in science

AI technologies have markedly improved the speed and scale of scientific work, but they have also enabled new forms of academic misconduct^{6,48-50}. These include AI-assisted data fabrication, automated generation of persuasive but fictitious datasets, and the use of AI tools to produce, adapt, or plagiarise text while obscuring sources^{6,49,50}. Deep learning models can generate highly realistic biomedical images and experimental results, and there are documented concerns about their misuse to fabricate or manipulate evidence, with serious implications for public health and safety^{6,50}.

Advanced AI tools have been used to generate or simulate clinical trial data; while simulation can sometimes be legitimate for modelling, using non-validated AI-generated data as if it were empirical can misinform research directions and risk public health⁴⁸. Natural language processing systems can produce literature reviews, research reports, and entire draft manuscripts, which may be submitted without proper disclosure or attribution^{49,50}. Generated or modified data and text using AI have the potential to mislead research results, distort theoretical developments, and undermine the originality and intellectual property rights of authors^{6,50}.

Empirical analyses of case studies on the misuse of AI have demonstrated that AI can be misapplied in different contexts, posing threats to research integrity^{6,48-50}. Fabricated AI-generated data undermine the core principles of scientific research by jeopardising reliability and reproducibility, leading others to build on fake or misleading results^{6,50}. Recent studies indicate that AI is already being used to produce pseudo-original scientific papers; the texts in these works are often plagiarised, violating authors' intellectual property rights and undermining the integrity and originality of the academic record⁵⁰.

3.3.3.4. Political influence and RM

The influence of politics on science and technology is a major concern for research integrity. The loss of public trust in science has broader epistemic and political consequences that are central themes in science and technology studies, public policy, and philosophy^{5,16,34,46}. When

the integrity of research is questioned, evidence-based policymaking and democratic governance are weakened^{16,34}. If the integrity of the scientific process itself is doubted, the public's rationale for trusting science collapses, making it harder for scientific consensus to influence public policy^{5,46}. Major cases of RM can severely damage the relationship between scientists and the public; when the public no longer believes that scientists are working in good faith, it becomes easier for misinformation to take root, making evidence-based policymaking extremely difficult, especially on politically charged topics such as public health or climate change^{16,34,46}.

Anti-science movements, populist groups, and authoritarian actors often exploit high-profile cases of RM to promote distrust in science and expertise⁵¹⁻⁵⁴. Public trust in science can be strategically eroded for political or economic gain, as seen in controversies where flawed or retracted studies are used to fuel conspiracy narratives and resistance to health guidance^{51,52}. The Surgisphere scandal during the COVID-19 pandemic, in which two high-impact COVID-19 studies based on dubious data were published and later retracted by leading journals, illustrated how problematic research can directly influence global health policy and then be weaponised by conspiracy theorists and anti-science movements to damage the public's willingness to follow subsequent health recommendations⁵².

This loss of trust is often capitalised on by actors who present themselves as authentic alternatives to a supposedly corrupt scientific establishment⁵¹⁻⁵⁴. Additionally, political communication strategies can distort perceptions of research outcomes, as seen in cases where government communications during the COVID-19 pandemic contributed to declines in trust in science and vaccines^{48,51-53}. Such dynamics are compounded when fabricated data or implicated researchers are involved, further damaging public confidence. Deliberate creation of doubt or “manufactured ignorance” by powerful actors to protect their interests can delay acceptance of well-supported scientific findings, undermine the social contract between science and society, and hinder timely responses to pressing public challenges^{5,16,34,51-54}.

3.4. Case Example(s)

Case 1 Data falsification case

Researchers within a research group in a laboratory at University College London (UCL), headed by a professor of genetics and Vice-Chancellor of Birkbeck, University of London, were found by a university investigation to have published fraudulent papers with manipulated and falsified data over a number of years. UCL determined in its investigation that the head researcher was responsible for committing RM by running his lab in a “reckless” manner and adding himself as a co-author to fraudulent publications, although it acknowledged that this RM was not necessarily deliberate. However, investigations by journalists also discovered that UCL had hushed up whistleblower complaints and avoided investigating the lab a decade earlier to protect the university against reputational damage¹⁷.

Significant aspects: The case raises issues concerning senior academics' management of labs they run; in this case, the head researcher was found by an investigatory panel to be “reckless in the conduct of his lab” and to have committed RM by claiming co-authorship on papers written by colleagues under his supervision in his lab that used fabricated data. A mid-career researcher from the research group admitted to falsifying information in publication figures

and also attempted to pass blame on to junior researchers. Freedom of Information requests later showed that the UCL administration and the head researcher were aware of claims made by a junior researcher whistleblower as early as 2007 and tried to hush up the issue.

Outcome: After investigation, UCL found the head researcher to have committed RM in two investigations held in 2014/2015 but determined that there was insufficient evidence that this was deliberate, and thus no grounds for dismissal. Statements released by the head researcher and his lawyers stated he had been cleared in investigations, despite information that he had in fact been found to have committed RM being later discovered in 2019 through journalists' Freedom of Information Act requests to UCL, which UCL tried to block. The head researcher continues to hold his position as professor of genetics at UCL and vice-chancellor of Birkbeck. A co-author of one of the head researcher's papers who admitted manipulating research images in publications left UCL in 2013; he subsequently took up an academic position at the European University Cyprus and is now a professor there. The head researcher's department has so far retracted at least six papers and corrected two more. A former member of the research group resigned before UCL started a formal disciplinary action against the individual.

Case 2 Norwegian School of Sport Sciences (NIH) Health Research Act violation

Researchers at the Norwegian School of Sport Sciences (NIH) conducted and published a study involving human subjects and biological material without obtaining the mandatory prior approval from the Regional Committees for Medical and Health Research Ethics (REK), a direct violation of the Norwegian Health Research Act. Despite lacking this legal authorisation, the researchers published their findings in 2017, falsely claiming in the manuscript that the project had received the necessary ethical approvals. An investigation by the Norwegian Board of Health Supervision (Helsetilsynet) revealed that the institution had failed in its internal oversight and allowed research to proceed and be disseminated under false ethical pretences^{55,56}.

Significant aspects: The case represents a significant legal violation with breach of the Health Research Act, moving the misconduct from a purely academic concern to a legal and regulatory violation. The investigation highlighted that NIH, as a research institution, did not have sufficient control systems to ensure that its researchers followed statutory ethical requirements before starting data collection. The researchers explicitly misled the scientific community and journal editors by stating that ethical approval had been granted when, in fact, it had never been applied for or received for that specific project.

Outcome: The Norwegian Board of Health Supervision issued a formal decision finding NIH in breach of the law. The institution was ordered to immediately stop all ongoing research related to the project and to destroy all biological material and data collected during the unauthorised period. NIH was ordered to withdraw all published articles based on illegal material. The institution was required to overhaul its internal "System for Quality Assurance" to prevent future violations of the Health Research Act.

Case 3 Retaliation and discrimination concerns at Oslo University Hospital (OUS)

An international PhD candidate working at OUS sued the hospital, alleging severe reprisals after she reported a toxic work environment and poor academic supervision. The candidate

alleged that her scholarship was revoked, her research materials were destroyed, and she was forced onto unfair short-term contracts that jeopardised her residency permit in Norway. OUS denied the accusations, characterising the student as a “very demanding employee” and arguing that her complaints did not constitute formal whistleblowing under the Working Environment Act. While the hospital won both the District Court and the Court of Appeal, the appellate ruling was not unanimous, with a minority of judges believing she had indeed been subjected to reprisals^{57,58}.

Significant aspects: Power asymmetry is an important highlight; this case was described by the Research Ombudsman as a prime example of “power arrogance” and the exploitation of a junior researcher within a rigid academic hierarchy. It highlights whistleblower vulnerability and showcases the extreme professional and personal risks faced by international researchers, particularly those on visas, when reporting institutional misconduct or poor environments. A critical and rare aspect of this case was the allegation that research material was destroyed as a form of professional punishment, directly impacting the candidate’s ability to complete her doctoral work. The hospital’s strategy centred on “character defamation”, shifting the focus from the reported environment to the personality of the whistleblower.

Outcome: The Norwegian courts ruled in favour of Oslo University Hospital, finding insufficient evidence that the hospital’s actions were illegal “reprisals”. Despite the legal win for OUS, prominent ethics professors and the Research Ombudsman criticised the hospital’s witnesses as “dishonest” and the institution’s handling of the case as “ethically bankrupt”. The candidate was unable to secure further positions in Norway following the trial; she eventually moved abroad after being awarded a prestigious Marie Curie fellowship. The case remains a high-profile reference point in Norway for discussions on the lack of effective protection for PhD “whistleblowers” and the systemic tendency of institutions to protect their own reputation at the expense of junior staff.

3.5. Summary

- RM undermines the self-correcting nature of science by weakening the reliability of evidence and the trust on which knowledge production depends. It has system-wide consequences that reach beyond individual researchers to affect RPOs, RFOs, journals, policymakers, the wider scientific community, and even society.
- Institutions and publishers face reputational damage, heightened scrutiny, and pressure to strengthen oversight and accountability, while high-profile RM cases can trigger stricter regulatory and compliance demands that may both enhance accountability and constrain legitimate research activities.
- When RM distorts the evidence base for decision-making, it can lead to flawed policies, ineffective interventions, and harmful outcomes across sectors such as health, environment, agriculture, technology, climate, and other social systems; health-related RM is especially consequential, as it can compromise medical guidelines, public health measures, and individual and community safety.

- RM erodes trust not only in science but also in public institutions, industry (e.g. pharmaceutical and biomedical companies), and international organisations (e.g. WHO), fuelling broader scepticism towards vaccines, public health interventions, and scientific expertise.

The impacts of RM are distributed across many stakeholders: researchers (including early-career and marginalised groups), students, collaborators, and the scientific community; institutional actors such as RPOs, RFOs, publishers, and journals; governance and policy actors; practitioners who apply research in various sectors; research participants, patients, affected communities, and users of research-based products or policies; society at large; and case-specific actors such as whistleblowers, witnesses, respondents, and perpetrators, all of whom may face significant professional and personal consequences.

Statement on the Use of Generative AI in Producing Chapter 3

Chapter 3 of this Best Practices Manual was partially developed with the assistance of ChatGPT. It was used to organise references including existing BEYOND project content and to suggest phrasing that harmonises definitions, stakeholder descriptions, and contextual explanations. All substantive concepts, scope decisions, references, and final formulations have been drafted, reviewed and validated by the author. Responsibility for the chapter's content and the interpretation of the BEYOND framework rests with the named authors.

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Chapter 4: Preventing and Addressing Research Misconduct

Authors⁴

Eero Kaila, Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK
Anni Sairio, Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK
Kalle Videnoja, Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK
Kalypso Iordanou, UCLan Cyprus School of Sciences
Kadri Simm, University of Tartu

4.1. Overview and Relevance of the Chapter

Chapter 4 provides an overview of how RM can be prevented and addressed through clear, fair, and coordinated action at policy and institutional levels. It translates BEYOND Guideline Sections 2–11 into practical guidance for governance and oversight. It highlights why well-designed RM frameworks are essential for protecting RI, safeguarding the health and well-being of those involved in cases, and maintaining public trust in science and institutions. The chapter is particularly relevant for policymakers, RPOs, RFOs, and RIOs, as it shows how socio-economic impacts, research culture, power relations, and working conditions should be taken into account when developing procedures for prevention, reporting, investigation, sanctions, and follow-up. It also underscores the importance of support, learning mechanisms, and rehabilitation pathways, encouraging these stakeholders to move beyond a purely punitive approach towards systems that both ensure accountability and strengthen the overall research environment.

4.2. Guideline References

The practices discussed in this chapter reflect and operationalise several Sections of the BEYOND Guidelines (Sections 2–11), which together address prevention, detection, handling, and follow-up of RM across the research ecosystem.

Section 2 (Addressing the Socio-economic Impacts of RM): Underlines that RM has wide-ranging scientific, economic, and societal consequences and calls for proportionate, clearly justified responses that minimise harm while protecting research quality and public trust.

⁴ Author contribution statement: *Eero Kaila, Anni Sairio and Kalle Videnoja* (in alphabetical order) contributed the following sections: Addressing the Impacts of Research Misconduct, Establishing Trust: Public Engagement and Institutional Foundations, Fostering a Supportive and Responsible Research Culture, Recommendations for Handling RM Allegations, Whistleblowing and Whistleblower Protection, Implementation Tips and Tools, and the ethical review case example. *Kadri Simm* contributed the section on Restoration of Trust after Research Misconduct Investigations and the Rehabilitation case examples. *Kalypso Iordanou* contributed the section The Role of Nudges in Sensitising Researchers on Research Misconduct and Unacceptable Practices.

Section 3 (Health and Well-being of Researchers): Highlights the importance of safe, inclusive working environments and recognises that procedures for preventing and handling RM must take account of stress, job insecurity, and unequal power relations that can both contribute to RM and affect those caught up in cases.

Section 4 (Establishing Trust: Public Engagement and Institutional Foundations): Emphasises transparency, openness, and honest communication about RM cases and institutional responses, so that public trust in science and in research institutions is maintained or restored.

Section 5 (Fostering a Supportive and Responsible Research Culture): Links responsible research culture and incentive structures to the likelihood of RM and CRPs, and calls on RPOs, RFOs, and leaders to align assessment, promotion, and funding with integrity-supportive practices.

Section 6 (Handling RM Allegations): Sets out principles for receiving, assessing, and investigating allegations, including clear procedures, independence and expertise of investigative bodies, contextual assessment, and fair treatment of all parties.

Section 7 (Addressing RM and Contestable Practices): Distinguishes between RM, CRPs, and honest error, and encourages tailored responses ranging from correction and mentoring to formal sanctions, coupled with efforts to address underlying structural causes.

Section 8 (Support and Learning Mechanisms): Frames RM cases as opportunities for institutional learning, recommending systematic analysis of root causes, organisational feedback loops, and improvements in policies, training, and support structures.

Section 9 (Rehabilitation and Reintegration of Researchers after RM): Promotes proportionate, time-limited sanctions and fair pathways for rehabilitation and reintegration where appropriate, balancing accountability, prevention, and the long-term health of the research community.

Section 10 (Whistleblowing and Whistleblower Protection): Stresses the need for safe, confidential reporting channels, robust protection against retaliation, and explicit attention to power imbalances and intersectional vulnerabilities among potential whistleblowers.

Section 11 (Nudges and Behavioural Interventions): Encourages the use of behavioural insights—such as prompts, default options, and checklists—to support everyday responsible practice and lower the threshold for early discussion of concerns before they escalate into RM.

4.3. Explanation of the BEYOND Sections

4.3.1. Addressing the Impacts of Research Misconduct

The BEYOND Guidelines Section (GS) 2 sets out policy and governance expectations for how RPOs, RFOs and RE/RI bodies should handle and prevent RM. Section 3 sets out principles for making research integrity inseparable from equality, inclusion, and researcher well-being. The sections posit that ethical research depends on fair, safe, and supportive working conditions.

Research misconduct has far-reaching consequences that may damage careers, waste resources, jeopardise well-being, and undermine trust in science for both researchers and the general public. To address these impacts, it is best to invest in preventive measures. The following practices for addressing the impact of RM are recommended to mitigate harm and protect trust in research.

Policymakers

- Ensure that research actors commit to adhering to shared RE/RI principles and processes at the national level.
- Establish processes for the handling and investigation of RM allegations. *Example:* All organisations in Finland that are signatories of the *Finnish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity* commit to investigating RM allegations in the so-called RI process. The Finnish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity also provides information on how the RI process is carried out.
- Provide regulatory frameworks and oversight mechanisms for both public and private research that balance transparency with commercial confidentiality.

RPOs

- Provide clear and accessible information on how notifications of alleged RM are made, how RM allegations are handled, what consequences confirmed RM cases have, and who determines these consequences.
- Invest in prevention by providing guidance and training that are embedded into organisational culture and everyday research practice, and by supporting a culture of open dialogue.
- Mitigate harms caused by RM through transparent investigation processes, whistleblower protection and appropriate forms of communication.

RFOs

- Define and communicate in funding calls and funding decisions how confirmed RM and QRP cases affect the eligibility of applicants and what consequences they have during and after a funding period.
- Require applicants to identify risks and plan actionable strategies to mitigate these risks. *Example:* Include an RE/RI-related risk and mitigation section in applications. Where feasible, specify accountability measures linked to retractions due to RM.

Publishers

Define and communicate how notifications of alleged RM are made, how RM allegations related to manuscripts and publications are handled, and what consequences confirmed RM cases have.

RE/RI bodies and RIOs

Strengthen the cooperative RE/RI framework among RPOs and RFOs at the national level, provide information on the state of RE/RI, and help develop best practices. *Examples:* Develop guidance and materials that apply across disciplines and research activities; monitor the state of research culture through national barometer surveys; coordinate the work of, and communication between, organizational and regional ethics committees; establish national research integrity adviser systems.

4.3.2. Establishing Trust: Public Engagement and Institutional Foundations

BEYOND GS 4 explains how RPOs, RFOs, policymakers, and researchers can strengthen and sustain public trust in science as well as the trust of researchers in science by improving communication, transparency, and inclusiveness in RE/RI practices.

Establishing Trust across the Research Lifecycle

RI is the cornerstone of public and academic trust in science, ensuring that research is conducted with honesty, transparency, and accountability. It is fundamental to excellence in research and lies at the core of the research enterprise. It provides the foundation for trust among researchers and in the research record, and, equally importantly, underpins society's trust in research evidence and expertise.

Although instances of RM are impossible to predict, organisations can strengthen their resilience through preventive measures and mitigate harms, should RM occur. Trust in research is further strengthened through inclusive engagement of research participants and communities, and through institutional safeguards throughout the life-cycle of a research project, from planning to execution, publishing and dissemination.

Planning and design stage

1. Co-design research aims, questions, and methods with relevant communities, especially marginalised and Indigenous groups, and with particular care towards how the research affects these groups or draws on their contexts, knowledge or data. *Example:* Establish a community or public advisory group (e.g., patient/public representatives, local community organisations, Indigenous governance bodies) to formulate research questions, data governance, recruitment plans, and benefit-sharing, and document how their input has changed the design.
2. Use ethical review as a safeguard to identify and mitigate potential risks. *Examples:* Involve an ethics committee or other support early and revisit ethical considerations when methods change; ensure that researchers know how to access advice quickly if dilemmas arise.
3. Plan for inclusion by identifying barriers to participation and arranging practical support from the outset. The ethical review process should not be too paternalistic or overly protective towards research participants belonging to marginalised groups. *Examples:* Plan and budget for translation and/or interpretation, accessible materials (including plain-language summaries) and compensation for time and expertise.
4. Build integrity and trust into the project by clarifying roles, conflicts of interest, and public communication responsibilities early on. *Examples:* Require transparent

conflict-of-interest declarations for the research team and external partners; agree on authorship roles and requirements, publication rights and data access in contracts; draft a communication plan that anticipates likely misunderstandings (GS 4.1.–4.2.).

5. Make procedures easy to access and apply so that trust is supported by clarity and not simply assumed. *Example:* Provide a small-scale “integrity pack” for research partners, with links to relevant institutional policies and guidelines, reporting routes, templates e.g. for consent and data management, and a short overview of key responsibilities (GS 4.3.).

Execution and data collection stage

1. Ensure ongoing and respectful engagement with participants and communities where appropriate; treat trust as a relationship that needs maintenance. *Example:* Use iterative consent and regular check-ins for studies involving sensitive topics or vulnerable groups; share interim learning where appropriate.
2. Ensure that engagement with marginalised groups is safe, non-extractive, and attentive to power dynamics in fieldwork and collaboration. *Example:* Use culturally safe approaches where relevant; work through trusted intermediaries; set clear expectations for respectful conduct; provide a route to confidentially report harms or ethical concerns without fear of retaliation.
3. Support researchers working in politicised or high-scrutiny areas with institutional guidance that protects the researchers and others involved from undue pressure and guarantees methodological rigour. *Example:* Prepare researchers for hostile attention (including online harassment) and ensure access to institutional support services and leadership backing if public controversy escalates.

Publishing and dissemination stage

1. Communicate findings openly, accurately, and accessibly. Address possible concerns proactively in a transparent way (GS 4.1.–4.2.). *Example:* Publish plain-language summaries alongside academic outputs, when feasible and relevant; communicate clearly any limitations and uncertainties related to the research.
2. Share results with communities and research participants in ways that are meaningful to them and acknowledge contributions fairly. *Example:* Provide accessible summaries in relevant languages; consider co-authorship, acknowledgements, or other recognition where community partners have contributed to design, data gathering and analysis, or dissemination.
3. Protect trust through responsible corrections and coordinated communication when problems arise, balancing transparency with confidentiality obligations (GS4.5.). *Example:* If errors are identified, act promptly to issue corrections and inform relevant stakeholders (e.g., journals, funders, partners).

Institutional foundation stage

1. Ensure that RE/RI policies and procedures are clear, concise, actionable, and easy to find, and that they are embedded in training, supervision, and professional development (**GS 4.3.–4.4.**). *Example:* RPOs and other relevant bodies can maintain a well-publicised policy hub with guidance and templates.
2. Demonstrate ethical leadership and accountability. Institutions and senior researchers should model ethical conduct, manage conflicts of interest transparently, and promote a culture where raising concerns is safe and valued. *Example:* RPOs and other relevant bodies can provide leadership training that includes ethical decision-making, conflict-of-interest management, and supportive responses to concerns. Responsible practices should be embedded into evaluation criteria.
3. Engage stakeholders across the research ecosystem to maintain trust as an ongoing responsibility (**GS 4.5.**). *Example:* Policymakers and national RE/RI bodies can convene multi-stakeholder advisory panels (researchers, funders, journals, public/community representatives, and private-sector partners) to review RE/RI policies, identify emerging challenges, and co-develop trust-building activities.

4.3.3. Fostering a Supportive and Responsible Research Culture

The BEYOND GS 5 emphasises that research integrity (RI) and research ethics (RE) should be fostered through an open, inclusive, and discipline-sensitive research culture. The section encourages institutions to develop a living culture of integrity rooted in dialogue, shared understanding, and context-sensitive practices, rather than relying only on compliance mechanisms and sanctions (GS5.1.–5.6.).

Fostering a responsible culture goes beyond compliance and sanctions. Evidence suggests that workplace culture, leadership, and peer norms may have a stronger influence on responsible research conduct than rules and training alone^{1,2,3,4}. Institutions therefore play a decisive role in shaping the working culture and everyday practices.

Institutions shape research culture. Research organisations carry the main responsibility for promoting good practices, providing training, and ensuring supportive structures that build trust and integrity.

1. Organisational culture and leadership are key. Leadership and workplace culture are essential for maintaining integrity and research quality (**GS 5.1.**). *Example:* Provide leadership and supervision training that includes responsible mentoring, managing power dynamics, and responding constructively to ethical uncertainties; establish local “RI champions” or contact persons who facilitate regular, low-threshold discussions (e.g., ethics cafés, integrity roundtables) within departments or research groups.
2. Building a responsible research culture requires proactive measures, such as discussions, leadership training, and open dialogue, rather than placing primary focus on rules, sanctions, or formal training alone (**GS 5.1., 5.4., 5.5.**). *Example:* Integrate RI/RE into everyday research routines through practical supports: accessible guidance on data management, authorship, and conflicts of interest; open science support; and institutional “honour code” style commitments combined with recurring team-based reflection on what responsible practice means in that context.

3. Authorship agreements prevent conflicts. Early-stage and clear agreements on authorship roles and responsibilities, maintained as living documents, help manage expectations, prevent disputes, and support fair collaboration. Good research practices are linked with good project management. *Example:* Require an authorship discussion at project start (and at key milestones), supported by a simple template that records agreed contribution criteria, anticipated outputs, and a process for revisiting decisions as roles evolve.
4. Engage stakeholders across the research ecosystem. Effective RI/RE governance benefits from involving relevant stakeholders to ensure balanced, transparent, and context-sensitive guidance (**GS 5.2., 5.6.**). *Example:* Establish cross-disciplinary working groups and periodic consultations (including early-career researchers and relevant support staff) to co-develop and pilot RI/RE procedures; use structured feedback mechanisms to refine guidance so it remains workable across disciplines and research settings.
5. Diversity and accessibility strengthen integrity. Providing materials in accessible languages and avoiding hegemonic assumptions, such as privileging English-language norms, supports equitable participation and consistent understanding across the research community (**GS 5.3.**). *Example:* Offer key policies, reporting information, and training materials in the main working languages of the institution; develop multilingual glossaries of core RE/RI concepts; and ensure that guidance distinguishes clearly between unacceptable research practices and contextually justified disciplinary variation, without weakening the shared definition of RM.

4.3.4. Recommendations for Handling RM Allegations

The BEYOND Guidelines Section 6 sets out how allegations of RM should be handled fairly, transparently, and competently. Section 7 addresses how to manage politically sensitive or controversial cases, including safeguards against misuse of allegations. Section 8 highlights the importance of support for those involved and institutional learning from cases.

Shared standards and fair procedures of investigation are key starting points for handling allegations of RM and QRP. The *ENRIO Recommendations for the Investigation of Research Misconduct* (ENERI Consortium 2020)⁵ provide practical guidance on how allegations of RM should be investigated, taking into account significant differences among European systems. The handbook is based on the principle that all European countries, research institutions, and researchers should adhere to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

The Manual recommends a structured, phased investigation process that begins with a preliminary evaluation to determine whether the allegation falls under the domain of RI and should therefore be investigated through this process. If so, a more detailed investigation or inquiry phase by an expert committee is launched. The process concludes with a comprehensive report. Throughout, the process should ensure fairness, confidentiality, transparency, procedural integrity, protection of all parties, and the opportunity for appeal or a second opinion.

Investigation processes should take disciplinary practices and methodological norms into account when assessing allegations. The definition of RM nevertheless remains the same

across fields, and disciplinary variation cannot be used to justify misconduct or unacceptable research practices.

Institutions must protect researchers from harm and make it clear that investigation processes are based on guidelines and evidence, not ideology (**GS7.1.**). The Horizon Europe project PREPARED has drawn up a report on the harassment of researchers⁶ that charges institutions with the responsibility to proactively safeguard the well-being of researchers, to enable safe reporting, and to build cultures of integrity and trust in science.

Data from, for example, the Finnish Research Integrity Barometer (2023) indicate that only a small proportion of suspicions are formally reported or investigated, mainly due to fear of personal consequences. This emphasises the need for safe reporting processes and credible protection of whistleblowers.

Bad Apples for the Unforeseeable Future? Food for Thought

The ENRIO handbook, *Recommendations for the Investigation of Research Misconduct*⁷, recommends that when hiring researchers, institutions should ensure that candidates have not engaged in misconduct and are not under investigation. It can be argued that institutions have a duty of care to publish the results of RM investigations and the names of culprits. Sharing this information and flagging those who have committed RM when they change organisations could help to ensure that they cannot continue unacceptable practices elsewhere.

At the same time, considerations of confidentiality, rehabilitation, and proportionality must guide how such information is managed. Should this information follow a researcher throughout their career? If so, for what period of time, given that serious breaches should, and often already do, result in temporary bans from applying for research funding? Is there evidence-based reason to assume that those who have committed ethical breaches are likely to repeat their offences, or are some of these cases better understood as resulting from ignorance or inadequate training?

4.3.5. Whistleblowing and Whistleblower Protection

BEYOND GS 10 addresses how RPOs and policymakers should create a safe and fair environment for reporting RM and protecting those who report their concerns.

Individuals who report suspected breaches of good research practices are referred to as whistleblowers. Whistleblowing can take many forms. Some whistleblowers have a direct personal connection to the case, while others (such as so-called RI sleuths) may not. In certain situations, the *parties* involved may accuse one another of misconduct; in cases of *weaponised whistleblowing*, allegations are made in bad faith with the intent to harm.

Whistleblowers may face retaliation, marginalisation, or accusations of vigilantism. Those who suspect misconduct may therefore weigh potential personal consequences before deciding whether to report.

Institutions can adopt formal whistleblower protection policies at both national and institutional levels, aligned with international standards^{8,9,10}. Particular attention is needed for early-career researchers, students, and others in vulnerable or lower hierarchical positions.

The protection of whistleblowers: best practices for organisations

- Establish clear, accessible, and secure reporting channels and provide opportunities for confidential advice before a formal report is made. For example, appoint a trained contact point (e.g., ombudsperson/RI adviser) for confidential consultation, and clearly explain what will happen next if a concern proceeds to a formal process.
- Implement a whistleblower management system (WMS) that ensures impartial handling, confidentiality safeguards, and competent case management. Offer secure reporting channels that also ensure fair handling of notifications.
- Act promptly to prevent prolonged harm, communicate the steps of the process to those involved and avoid public statements that could stigmatise any party before the investigation has been carried out.
- Protect against retaliation, recognising that it may be subtle, indirect, or delayed. For example, follow-up check-ins at agreed intervals can be arranged with whistleblowers who consent to being contacted.
- Provide practical support to those involved, recognising the stress and risks associated with RM processes.
- Embed information about the process of handling allegations and whistleblower protection into RI training and everyday culture so that raising concerns in good faith is understood as responsible practice. Clarify rights and responsibilities so that uncertainty about process does not deter reporting.

4.3.6. Restoration of Trust after Research Misconduct Investigations

The BEYOND GS 9 proposes how RPOs should handle the reintegration and rehabilitation of researchers after an investigation of RM, both for those cleared of wrongdoing and for those found guilty but seeking to rebuild trust and contribute again.

Restoration of trust involves rehabilitation and reintegration with the aim of rebuilding relationships within the research community, when this is possible. **Rehabilitation** is about re-establishing professional capacity and standing, an evaluative process aimed at answering the question – is this person fit to be trusted as a responsible researcher? **Reintegration** is the practical process by which this is carried out, i.e., how and under what conditions the researcher will resume his/her activities.

Why are rehabilitation and reintegration important? Researchers are highly trained experts whose work is socially valuable and substantial resources have already been invested in their training and development. Moreover, not all cases of RM result from intentional wrongdoing, although ignorance or indifference does not excuse such conduct. Finally, even those who have engaged in misconduct intentionally may warrant an opportunity for repentance, learning and moral repair.

Institutions also have an ethical duty to actively restore the exonerated researcher's professional standing and support their well-being. Their wishes must be respected regarding

the extent to which they want the outcome of the investigation to be made public. Clear, standardised frameworks help ensure equal treatment across cases. Institutions should foster a non-stigmatising culture that focuses on recovery and integrity in the spirit of restorative justice rather than punishment.

Those found to have committed RM can be supported through tailored approaches, for example the support of ombudspersons or RI advisors. Reintegration should be based on the principles of fairness, proportionality, and belief in rehabilitation and based on the wish of the researcher to be rehabilitated. The process must be respectful and account for the fact that RM cases are highly diverse. Sanctions should match the intentionality and seriousness of the offence. RPOs must ensure that reintegration does not turn public shaming or exclusion.

If misconduct allegations impact whole research teams, institutions should offer collective support. This can include group counselling, reflective workshops, and leadership training to restore trust.

Practical implementations

- Standard reintegration protocols with clear steps, milestones (e.g., trainings passed) and timelines (time under mentorship) for returning to research roles.
- Confidential debrief meetings with cleared researchers, including communication support if they choose public disclosure.
- Ombudsperson or mentoring support for individuals found to have committed misconduct.
- Proportionate sanctions to ensure consistent treatment across cases and align consequences with severity.
- Restorative team sessions (e.g., group counselling, facilitated reflection workshops) after unit-wide allegations to rebuild trust and clarify expectations.
- Well-being services referral pathways for affected researchers, including counselling and stress-management support.
- Leadership guidance for supervisors on managing reintegration sensitively and avoiding stigma.
- Communication strategies that balance privacy concerns with transparency for both internal and external audiences.

Key messages

- Those wrongly accused must have their reputation restored.
- The research community should also consider the means by which those found responsible are guided to act responsibly in the future.

4.3.7. The Role of Nudges in Sensitising Researchers on Research Misconduct and Unacceptable Practices

The BEYOND GS 11¹¹ explains how RPOs can use behavioural interventions known as nudges to encourage ethical conduct and strengthen RE/RI. This approach connects behavioural science with integrity management, showing how small, well-designed changes in the research environment can promote responsible behaviour.

Example of using Nudges as preventive tools for responsible research

Based on the experimental findings of BEYOND D3.2¹², nudges can serve as effective tools for promoting RI by subtly influencing researchers' decision-making processes without restricting their freedom of choice. The D3.2 study demonstrates that strategically designed nudges—specifically those highlighting personal values and potential consequences—can positively impact integrity-related decisions in research contexts.

When participants were prompted to reflect on core values such as honesty, respect for others, accountability, and integrity, or to consider potential negative consequences of RM (including damaged relationships, unemployment, and reputational harm), their evaluation and endorsement of high-integrity behaviours improved.

These results suggest that nudges prompting researchers to consider ethical implications at critical decision moments—when they face integrity dilemmas—can strengthen their commitment to responsible conduct. For example, pre-submission prompts for university theses and journal articles could ask researchers to confirm that their manuscript complies with core values of honesty and accountability, while also acknowledging that misconduct carries serious consequences for their career and reputation. These nudges could be embedded in statistical software, raised during lab discussions, or incorporated into supervisory meetings.

This nudge-based approach offers a promising, low-cost intervention for fostering RI, complementing traditional training and regulatory approaches by targeting the cognitive and motivational factors that influence behaviour at the point of decision. The experimental work on nudges in the BEYOND project suggests that nudges prompting consideration of values and consequences can support more ethical decision-making. Yet one-off presentation of nudges is not enough—sustainable ethical behaviour requires frequent reminders. Nudges therefore need to be systematically embedded in academic practice.

4.4. Implementation Tips and Tools: An Overview

Preventing and addressing RM is an endeavour that is not reducible to codes of conduct and compliance. Instead, it is an effort that needs to permeate organisational culture and everyday research practice.

1) *Clear procedures for handling allegations and protecting those involved.* Organisations should follow established procedures that guarantee fair investigation of suspected RI violations and protect both whistleblowers and those accused of RM.

2) *Training and competence-building tools.* Provide RE/RI training for researchers, supervisors, and leaders.

3) *Accessible guidance and low-threshold advisory support* Organisations can strengthen responsible practice by providing instructions and resources by ensuring that researchers can seek confidential guidance on ethical issues. Researchers can approach RI advisors or ombudspersons early, before concerns escalate, and during investigation processes.

4) *Authorship agreements*. To prevent conflicts and strengthen responsible conduct of research, RPOs should encourage early discussions about contributions and provide practical tools such as templates for authorship agreements, which can be maintained as living documents throughout a project.

5) *Organisational planning tool: Research Integrity Promotion Plan (RIPP)*. Organisations can create and implement a RIPP focused on a selected priority area. A RIPP is a tailored, actionable framework designed to help RPOs and RFOs cultivate responsible research practices, prevent misconduct, and handle potential RI violations, and it should be repeated at regular intervals¹³.

6) *Behavioural tools: nudges and integrity signals*. Nudges can complement training and policies when they are transparent, evidence-based, and embedded in the broader research culture. Examples include structured campaigns that promote mechanisms such as honour codes and other community cues that support self-regulation and reduce tolerance for RM.

7) *Coordination and learning beyond the organisation*. There is a benefit in national-level coordination and oversight to support procedural fairness and RE/RI frameworks. Organisations are encouraged to secure resources for networking across institutional boundaries, supporting shared learning and capacity-building.

4.5. Case Examples

Case 1- Guidance for Policymakers and RPOs: Ethical Review in Non-Medical Human Sciences

In Finland, the need for ethical review in non-medical research is decided on a case-by-case basis, depending on whether the research plan involves ethical risks. In Finland, ethical review by a human sciences ethics committee is expected when a study involves higher ethical risk, such as

- involving minors in contexts that raise consent concerns;
- when participation in the research deviates from the principle of informed consent;
- when the research involves sensitive topics that could cause significant harm to research participants or to researchers and their close ones.

The role of the REC is not to approve study designs. Instead, its purpose is to help researchers with ethical reflection and propose solutions that mitigate ethical risks. Many low-risk studies do not require formal review.

Committee members have multidisciplinary expertise, and they work independently of funding decisions. Nationally, the RI office (the Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK) provides guidelines and promotes consistency.

Compared to more compliance-heavy systems, where almost all research with human participants must pass through an approval pipeline, the Finnish model keeps the ethics review process meaningful, proportionate, and credible, and upholds good research practice through these means. This avoids overloading committees with low-risk work and encourages real ethical reflection instead of box-ticking.

Case 2 - Rehabilitation Example 1

In 2017, a well-established expert in soil erosion and land management of the University of Valencia, resigned from several editorial roles after an investigation revealed that he had manipulated citations in favour of his own work and affiliated journals, substantially inflating impact factors and prompting his departure from journals including *Land Degradation & Development*. Eight years later, in 2025, he was appointed to the editorial board of *International Soil and Water Conservation Research*, a journal co-published by Elsevier and China Science Publishing & Media. The journal's leadership defended the decision by emphasising his recognised expertise and ongoing contributions and stated that his appointment came after nomination and review by Editors-in-Chief, that he would operate under strict ethical monitoring, and that he would be restricted to review and recommendation duties rather than final editorial decisions.

This case highlights the complexities of accountability and reintegration in academic publishing, showing both ongoing reputational debate within the research community and the possibility of conditional re-engagement after past ethical breaches¹⁵.

Case 3 - Rehabilitation Example 2

In 2015, the U.S. Office of Research Integrity (ORI) issued formal findings that a former associate professor of medicine at Duke University, had engaged in RM by including falsified data in multiple grant applications and published studies on cancer genomics, leading to retraction of numerous papers and the termination of clinical trials based on his work. Under a voluntary settlement agreement, the associate professor neither admitted nor denied the misconduct findings but agreed that, if he secured employment in research involving Public Health Service support within five years (to 2020), his work would be subjected to formal supervision, certification of data integrity by his institution and other oversight conditions. He also volunteered to exclude himself from advisory roles for that period. After resigning from Duke in 2010 and a period practicing briefly as a physician, he later worked in clinical settings outside PHS-funded research (e.g., at the Cancer Center of North Dakota as of 2024) while his administrative ORI restrictions elapsed, illustrating a form of reintegration into professional work following structured oversight and sanction conditions¹⁵.

4.6. Summary

This chapter provides actionable best practices for BEYOND Guideline chapters **2–11** for strengthening RE/RI and for preventing and addressing RM and other unacceptable practices.

The themed sections below link the relevant guideline chapters to practical measures for organisations and researchers.

- *Addressing the Impacts of Research Misconduct*: outlines how to mitigate the harms of RM through preventive aim and established processes by policymakers, RPOs, RFOs, research publishers and RE/RI bodies. Preventive measures safeguard the quality of research and research practices.
- *Establishing Trust: Public Engagement and Institutional Foundations*: sets out how trust can be built across the research life-cycle through openness and inclusive engagement and with strong institutional foundations.
- *Fostering a Supportive and Responsible Research Culture*: works on the foundation that responsible research culture goes beyond compliance and sanctions. Preventive measures strengthen the culture of integrity and reduce the drivers of RM and unacceptable practices. Supportive and responsible research culture can be strengthened especially through fostering open dialogue, leadership and supervision practices, authorship agreements, stakeholder engagement, and accessible guidance.
- *Recommendations for Handling RM Allegations*: shared standards and fair, transparent procedures are essential in handling RM allegations, and they also support the prevention of RM and QRPs.
- *Whistleblowing and Whistleblower Protection*: underlines the central importance of safe reporting, with secure reporting channels and robust protection against retaliation against whistleblowers.
- *Restoration of Trust after Research Misconduct Investigations*: outlines how trust can be rebuilt by restoring reputations and guiding to act responsibly in the future through proportionate, context-sensitive measures.
- *The Role of Nudges in Sensitising Researchers on Research Misconduct and Unacceptable Practices*: describes how transparent and evidence-based behavioural nudges can complement training and policies by prompting reflection at key decision points and making responsible choices easier within a broader ethical research culture. Nudges are subtle, non-restrictive interventions that alter the research environment to encourage ethical choices.

4.7. Further Reading and Resources

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Chapter 5: Research Ethics and Research Integrity Training

Authors⁵

Anu Tammeleht, University of Helsinki

Erika Löfström, University of Helsinki

5.1. Overview and Relevance of this Chapter

This chapter is relevant for higher education and research institutions as it addresses the critical need for fostering a culture of ethical conduct in research. As institutions increasingly focus on the integrity of academic work, this chapter provides comprehensive guidelines to develop effective training programs that equip researchers, including students and junior staff, with the necessary knowledge, skills, and values to navigate ethical challenges. By emphasizing the role of mentors and supervisors in promoting ethical practices, the chapter highlights the importance of leadership in cultivating an environment of accountability and responsibility. Furthermore, the inclusion of diverse pedagogical strategies ensures that training is not only engaging but also applicable to real-world scenarios, thereby enhancing ethical decision-making. The emphasis on evaluating training effectiveness underscores the commitment to continuous improvement and adaptation in response to emerging ethical dilemmas in research. Overall, this chapter serves as a vital resource for institutions aiming to uphold the highest standards of research integrity and ethics, ultimately contributing to the credibility and reliability of academic endeavours.

5.2. Guideline References

The practices discussed in this chapter build directly on several sections of the BEYOND Guidelines that address the purpose, design, and evaluation of RE/RI training.

Section 12 (Importance of RE/RI Training) underlines the need for continuous education that develops not only knowledge but also skills, values, and habits, and stresses that training should empower researchers to self-regulate their behaviour and understand the wider societal consequences of lost trust in science.

Section 13 (The Role of RE/RI Training for Mentors and Supervisors) highlights that senior researchers and supervisors have a key responsibility for shaping research culture, and calls on RPOs to provide them with targeted, ongoing training so they can model and support ethical conduct in their teams.

⁵ Author contribution statement: Both authors contributed significantly to the development and completion of this chapter. EL and AT conceived the chapter's core thematic framework, drafted the initial manuscript, made subsequent text revisions, and critically reviewed, edited, and approved the final version for publication.

Section 14 (Pedagogy for RE/RI Training) emphasises that training should be adaptive, reflective, emotionally engaging, and embedded in collaborative learning, using tools such as self-reflection apps, group discussions, role-play, and real-world ethical dilemmas to connect principles with practice for both researchers and citizen scientists.

Section 15 (Indicators of Effectiveness of RE/RI Training) urges RPOs and trainers to use structured evaluation frameworks, combine quantitative and qualitative methods, and ensure that learning analytics and assessments are used transparently to improve training rather than punish learners, while sharing evaluation outcomes to promote best practices and a broader culture of RI across the research community.

Relevant Stakeholders and Contexts

This chapter is relevant for a number of stakeholders, such as *researchers, citizen scientists and students for whom* the training aims to empower them with the knowledge, skills, values, and habits necessary for ethical research practices, particularly in contexts where attention to ethics is vital; for *mentors and supervisors* to enhance their leadership roles in fostering an ethical research culture and to support junior researchers in navigating ethical challenges; *RPOs* responsible for implementing effective training programs and ensuring ongoing education in RE/RI, as well as ensuring the effectiveness of these programs; *RFOs* to emphasize the requirement that funded researchers and their institutions adhere to RE/RI standards; and *policymakers* needing understanding of how research environments operate and which factors promote or undermine ethical research practices.

In which contexts is this chapter relevant:

1. *Academic institutions:* universities and colleges that conduct research require robust RE/RI training programs for faculty, researchers, and students to ensure that ethical standards are upheld in research activities.
2. *RPOs:* RPOs and think tanks must ensure an ethical research culture among their staff and collaborators and RE/RI training may be the best way to achieve this.
3. *Public and private sector research:* organisations involved in applied research, including government agencies and private companies, need to prioritise RE/RI training to navigate the complexities of research that may have significant societal implications.
4. *International research collaborations:* in contexts where researchers from different countries and institutions collaborate, RE/RI training is crucial to align ethical standards and practices across diverse cultural and regulatory environments.
5. *RFOs:* organisations that provide funding for research projects should emphasise the importance of RE/RI training in ensuring that grant recipients adhere to ethical guidelines.
6. *Professional development programs:* workshops, seminars, and training sessions aimed at enhancing the skills of researchers, especially for early-career researchers and students, should incorporate RE/RI principles.

7. *Policy development*: policymakers involved in crafting regulations and guidelines for scientific research benefit from understanding which factors promote/undermine ethical research practices and how RE/RI training can be a powerful vehicle for promoting a culture of integrity.
8. *Community engagement and citizen science*: involving the public in research initiatives requires RE/RI training to ensure that all participants, including citizen scientists, understand their roles and responsibilities.
9. *Online learning environments*: as more training moves to digital platforms, the relevance of accessible and adaptable RE/RI training materials becomes critical for catering to broad and diverse audiences.
10. *Crisis management and response*: in situations where RE/RI breaches occur, having established RE/RI training can help organisations respond effectively and mitigate future risks.

5.3. Explanation of the BEYOND Sections

Chapter 5 is mostly based on the research carried out in WP4, specifically Deliverables 4.1 and 4.2^{1,2}.

5.3.1. Importance of RE/RI Training

The BEYOND Guidelines³ sections and sub-section on RE/RI training outline that RPOs and educators should provide continuous, inclusive training that builds knowledge, skills, values, and habits to empower researchers to self-regulate—especially in high-risk practices like selective analysis—through pedagogy that is active, field-specific, case-based, and embedded in supportive supervision and collaboration contexts (**GS12.1-12.4**). This integrated requirement matters because it simultaneously mitigates ethical risks and misconduct, improves rigour, reproducibility and trustworthiness, cushions individuals against competition and publication pressures, and fortifies public trust by clarifying how lapses fuel misinformation that can be exploited by anti-science, populist, or authoritarian actors to weaken science and democratic institutions (**GS12.1, 12.3, 12.4**). Stakeholders include RPO leadership, department heads, supervisors, and RE/RI educators as leads for designing and resourcing programs, while students, junior and senior researchers, administrative staff, and external collaborators are both beneficiaries and co-responsible participants who enact practices and provide feedback within safe learning environments (**GS12.1, 12.3**). In practice, application should weave together active learning (simulations, realistic case studies, peer dialogue), field-tailored modules, mentorship with scheduled supervision checkpoints, collaboration agreements with clear RE/RI clauses, and explicit teaching of guidelines alongside societal impacts of distrust, delivered through onboarding, lab meetings, graduate seminars, and cross-institutional workshops that normalise reflection and learning from mistakes (**GS12.2, 12.3, 12.4**). Expected outcomes include fewer questionable practices, stronger data transparency and management, higher trustworthiness, improved working climate, greater use of safe reporting channels without retaliation, and demonstrable competence on scenario-based assessments, indicating a self-regulating culture (**GS12.1-12.4**). These sub-sections interlock with broader themes of responsible research culture,

openness and accountability, mentoring quality, and collaboration governance, reinforcing coherence with related guidance on RM prevention, transparency norms, and public engagement, while the pedagogical emphasis and supervision safeguards serve as connective tissue across **GS12.1–12.4**.

5.3.2. Role of RE/RI Training for Mentors and Supervisors

The sections indicate that RPOs should deliver targeted, regular, and continuous RE/RI training to senior researchers and supervisors so they can actively lead and sustain an ethical research culture, and for those leaders to assume clear responsibility for modelling, supervising, and mentoring ethical conduct within their teams (**GS13.1, 13.2**). This matters because mentor and supervisor behaviour is a primary lever for mitigating ethical risks, improving rigor and trustworthiness, and shaping daily norms—thereby reducing misconduct, strengthening team cohesion, and reinforcing public trust in science. Lead stakeholders are RPO leadership, research directors, and RE/RI educators who design and resource the training, while senior researchers and supervisors are accountable implementers; affected and supporting stakeholders include postdocs, students, research staff, and collaborators whose practices are shaped by mentorship and supervision (**GS13.1, 13.2**). In practice, implementation should integrate leader-focused modules on ethical decision-making, oversight of practices, feedback and coaching skills, and creating psychologically safe environments, combined with structured supervision checkpoints, mentoring plans, and explicit team charters that embed RE/RI expectations into lab meetings, onboarding, and collaboration agreements (**GS13.1, 13.2**). Expected outcomes include demonstrable mentor competencies on scenario-based assessments, improved work climate, reduction in questionable research practices, timely resolution of concerns without retaliation, transparent authorship and data management, and positive trainee progression indicating healthy, ethical teams (**GS13.1, 13.2**). These provisions connect to broader themes of responsible research culture, supervision quality, and collaboration governance, dovetailing with comprehensive RE/RI training for all researchers and reinforcing the leadership mechanisms introduced in Section 12 to ensure coherent, organisation-wide ethical practice⁴.

5.3.3. Pedagogy for RE/RI Training

The sections on pedagogy outline the importance of a comprehensive framework for RE/RI training that is adaptable, reflective, collaborative, and accessible, ensuring that researchers are well-equipped to navigate ethical challenges encountered in their professional lives.

They encourage RPOs and educators to design learner-centred, practice-oriented training that personalizes instruction through adaptive tools (e.g., self-reflection apps, ethical sensitivity measures) (**GS14.1**)⁵, embeds continuous reflective learning for all researchers and citizen scientists (**GS14.2**), makes group discussions and collaborative activities a core element for ethical deliberation and teamwork (**GS14.3**), leverages emotionally engaging methods like live case studies and role-playing to connect awareness with moral reasoning (**GS14.4**), and consistently uses ethical dilemmas and real-world applications to bridge theory and practice (**GS14.5**), while ensuring that researchers who involve citizen scientists provide RE/RI training and that materials are versatile, FAIR-aligned, and accessible across formats and online platforms (**GS14.6**). This integrated pedagogy matters because it mitigates ethical blind spots, strengthens critical thinking and decision-making, increases engagement, and builds a resilient culture capable of navigating complex, real-world ethics, thereby improving research

quality and public trust (GS14.1–14.5). Lead stakeholders include RPO leadership, programme designers, and RE/RI educators responsible for resourcing and structuring the curriculum, with researchers (senior and junior) and citizen scientists as co-producers and beneficiaries who enact, reflect on, and assess ethical practice. Support roles include IT services for adaptive tools and accessibility, and team leads who enable training (GS14.1–14.6). In application, programmes should combine adaptive diagnostics to tailor content, structured reflective journals, peer dialogue and teamwork tasks with follow-up mechanisms, scenario-based exercises and role-plays anchored in authentic dilemmas from specific fields, and modular, FAIR-compliant materials deliverable via online platforms for diverse contexts and distributed teams, with explicit expectations that researchers train citizen scientists when involved (GS14.1–14.6). Expected outcomes include improved ethical sensitivity, high-quality reflections evidencing principled reasoning, strong participation and mutual learning indicators in group work, demonstrable competence in scenario assessments, transfer of learning to lab and field decisions, and equitable access and usage analytics for training materials—collectively marking higher RE/RI competence and culture. These sections interlock with broader themes of responsible research culture, inclusivity, openness, and supervision quality, reinforcing field-wide commitments to effective pedagogy, practical application, and engagement of diverse research actors, building on existing prior training initiatives and broadening these to ensure organization-wide ethical practice.

5.3.4. Indicators of Effectiveness of RE/RI Training

This section highlights the importance of structured evaluation, continuous improvement, and collaboration in ensuring the effectiveness and impact of RE/RI training programs. By addressing these aspects, stakeholders can enhance the quality and relevance of training initiatives, ultimately fostering a culture of integrity.

RPOs and RE/RI trainers should design and run transparent, non-punitive evaluation systems that use structured frameworks and learning taxonomies to gauge progression from recall to higher-order ethical reasoning (GS15.1), responsibly deploy learning analytics and authentic manifestations of learning to capture engagement and decision processes (GS15.2)^{6,7}, conduct ongoing programme- or departmental-level evaluations that track long-term impacts on practice with opportunities for reflection⁸ and assurance that results are not used against learners (GS15.3), and establish continuous feedback loops with participants and faculty to iteratively improve content and delivery (GS15.4). They should combine quantitative and qualitative measures—surveys, pre/post assessments, focus groups, and quality checks of authentic outputs—for a comprehensive picture of knowledge, values, and behaviour change (GS15.5), and ensuring collaboration with ethics education experts to ground methods in best practice and current scholarship (GS15.6), with deliberation of evaluation outcomes to promote transparency and strengthen a wider culture of RI (GS15.7)^{9,10}. This matters because rigorous, learner-centred assessment mitigates ethical risk by strengthening learning, surfacing blind spots early, driving pedagogical improvement, and building trust through openness, ultimately enhancing research quality and integrity. Lead stakeholders are RPO leadership, programme directors, and RE/RI educators who design frameworks and safeguards, with researchers, students, and citizen scientists as participants whose practices inform longitudinal insights, and IT/data teams supporting analytics and accessibility; ethics education experts serving as co-designers (GS15.1–15.7). In application, RPOs should

implement multi-level evaluation plans that map learning objectives, instrument platforms to collect analytics in privacy-respecting ways, embed authentic tasks (e.g., case analyses, authorship decisions, data management plans), schedule periodic follow-ups on behavioural indicators, convene feedback sessions, and triangulate survey results with observed practice, while making aggregate findings available and sharing improvement actions (GS15.1–15.7). Expected outcomes include progression to higher-order ethical reasoning, sustained improvements in practice (fewer questionable behaviours, clearer authorship and data stewardship), high engagement, constructive feedback, validated instruments aligned with ethics education research, and community-wide adoption of effective practices following transparent dissemination. These Sections interlock with broader themes of effective pedagogy, continuous improvement, openness and accountability, and leadership responsibility, reinforcing prior training efforts and supervision by ensuring that RE/RI education is evidence-based, adaptive, and culturally embedded across the research organization.

5.4. Implementation Tips and Tools

The table below provides a structured approach for implementing the guidelines in chapter 5 including:

The main topic: key areas from the guidelines;

Recommendation: specific actions or strategies to achieve RE/RI training objectives;

Potential implementer: Research Performing Organizations (RPOs), RE/RI trainers, mentors, supervisors, and senior researchers;

Effectiveness measurement tools: suggestions based on Deliverable 4.2.

Main Topic	Recommendation	Responsibility	Effectiveness measurement tool
Importance of RE/RI Training	1. Incorporate active participation, field-specific content, and real-life case studies in training programs to promote desirable research behaviours.	RPOs and RE/RI trainers	ProLearning and ForgetNot: Collect learner reactions to specific activities and training sessions.
	2. Emphasize ongoing training to enhance ethical reasoning and awareness among researchers.	RPOs and RE/RI trainers	Self-reflection form/compass (SRF/SRC): Monitor learning process and provide insights on content understanding to facilitator and feedback to learners.
	3. Focus on supervision and training for students and junior researchers	Mentors and Supervisors	

	to manage ethical challenges effectively.		Learning diaries: Engage with the development of researchers' REI competencies over time.
Role of Mentors and Supervisors	1. Provide targeted RE/RI training for senior researchers to enhance leadership in fostering a culture of integrity.	RPOs, Mentors, and Supervisors	Self-reflection form/compass (SRF/SRC): Implement reflection into training for ethics competencies. Group discussions: Monitor understanding of topics through recorded discussions.
	2. Encourage senior researchers to actively promote ethical conduct within their teams.	Senior Researchers	
Pedagogy of RE/RI training	1. Implement adaptive teaching tools for personalized learning experiences.	RE/RI trainers	Domain-specific, domain-transcending measure: Assess ethical awareness across fields. Monitoring the online learning environment: Use platforms like Moodle to track learning outcomes. Pre- and post-texts: Measure retention and change in behavior/values post-training. Group reports/portfolios: Reflect
	2. Employ diverse assessment methods, including self-reflections and practical applications of ethical principles in addition to content knowledge on RE/RI.	RE/RI trainers	
	3. Incorporate reflective practices and collaborative activities to enhance ethical decision-making skills.	RE/RI trainers	
	4. Use emotional engagement strategies like role-playing to deepen understanding.	RE/RI trainers	

	5. Ensure training includes real-world ethical dilemmas for practical application.	RE/RI trainers	<p>advancement of knowledge and co-creation of knowledge.</p> <p>Impact of group dynamics: Monitor active participation and group dynamics during training.</p> <p>Using vignettes: Measure ethical sensitivity through scenario-based evaluations.</p>
Indicators of Effectiveness of RE/RI Training	1. Use structured evaluation frameworks to assess training outcomes.	RPOs and RE/RI trainers	<p>Retention check: Measure retention of competencies through the quality of ethics sections in texts such as theses, dissertations and articles.</p> <p>National surveys: Reflect macro-level impact of training on the research community.</p>
	2. Apply learning analytics to gauge participant engagement and decision-making.	RPOs and RE/RI trainers	
	3. Combine quantitative and qualitative measures for comprehensive evaluation.	RPOs and RE/RI trainers	
	4. Conduct ongoing evaluation to assess long-term impacts on ethical behaviour.	RPOs	<p>CoTrack: Monitor group dynamics and turn-taking during group work.</p> <p>Eye-tracking (for researchers): Provides insights into learner focus and attention during training.</p>
	5. Establish feedback mechanisms for continuous improvement of training programs.	RPOs and RE/RI trainers	
	6. Collaborate with ethics education experts to enhance training methodologies.	RPOs and RE/RI trainers	<p>Learning diaries: Engage with the development of</p>
	7. Share evaluation outcomes to promote	RPOs	

	best practices in the research community.		<p>researchers' REI competencies over time.</p> <p>Self-reflection form/compass (SRF/SRC): Implement reflection into training for ethics competencies.</p> <p>Domain-specific, domain-transcending measure: Combine measures for comprehensive RE/RI education.</p>
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5.5. Case Example(s)

An illustrative case: an ethical dilemma in a collaborative research project

A university research team, led by a senior researcher, is collaborating with a private pharmaceutical company, to develop a new drug aimed at treating a chronic illness. The research involves human clinical trials, and the team includes graduate students, postdoctoral researchers, and industry partners.

During the initial phases of the clinical trials, one of the graduate students discovers that the data from early trials suggests the drug may not be as effective as initially thought. However, the project is under significant pressure from the pharmaceutical company to produce positive results, as they have invested heavily in the research and are eager to move forward with marketing the drug.

Implementation of RE/RI Guidelines:

- Fostering Ethical Behaviour:** *The senior scientist organizes a mandatory RE/RI training session for her team, emphasizing the importance of transparency and integrity in research. They discuss the ethical implications of selective reporting and the potential harm to patients if the drug is marketed based on misleading data.*
- Active Participation and Realistic Scenarios:** *The training incorporates case studies, including similar real-world examples where researchers faced ethical dilemmas. Participants engage in group discussions to explore how they would handle similar situations, fostering a culture of open dialogue.*

3. **Role of Mentors and Supervisors:** *The senior scientist, as the supervisor, takes an active role in mentoring her team. She encourages the graduate student to voice his concerns, reinforcing that ethical conduct is paramount and that the team will support him in addressing any issues with pharmaceutical company.*
4. **Diverse Pedagogical Strategies:** *The team uses adaptive teaching tools, such as ethical sensitivity exercises, to help members recognize their biases and the potential consequences of their actions. They also utilize self-reflection apps to document their thoughts on ethical issues throughout the project.*
5. **Reflective Learning Practices:** *The graduate student keeps a learning diary where he reflects on the challenges faced during the trials and the importance of ethical decision-making. This practice helps him articulate his thoughts and prepares him for discussions with the senior scientist and the team.*
6. **Collaborative Activities:** *The research team holds regular meetings to discuss progress and ethical considerations. They implement tools to monitor participation and engagement, ensuring that all voices are heard, especially during discussions about the drug's efficacy.*
7. **Emotional Engagement:** *To deepen the team's connection to the ethical issues, the senior scientist organizes a role-playing session where team members act out scenarios involving ethical dilemmas. This exercise helps them empathize with the potential impact of their decisions on patients' lives.*
8. **Bridging Theory and Practice:** *Throughout the research process, the team continuously incorporates ethical dilemmas into their discussions, ensuring that they remain aware of the implications of their findings and decisions.*
9. **Measuring Effectiveness:** *After the training, the senior scientist implements a feedback mechanism where team members can share their thoughts on the training's effectiveness and suggest improvements for future sessions.*
10. **Ongoing Evaluation:** *The team conducts periodic assessments of their ethical decision-making processes, using both a quantitative survey and qualitative discussions to evaluate how well they are adhering to the RE/RI guidelines established during training.*

Outcome: *When the graduate student raises his concerns about the data, the senior scientist supports him in presenting the findings to the pharmaceutical company, advocating for transparency. The team collectively decides to pause the project until they can conduct further analysis and ensure that the drug's efficacy is accurately represented. This decision not only upholds ethical standards but also strengthens the team's integrity and commitment to responsible research.*

In addition, the senior scientist displays various REI leadership competencies, e.g. considering the team's need and ensuring they know that help is available; facilitating the trainings to cater for the needs of the team, also enacting as a role-model and displaying best research practices; she also shows commitment to the ethical practices and encourages others to do it too.

This case illustrates how the implementation of RE/RI training and guidelines can effectively foster an ethical research culture, empower researchers to navigate complex dilemmas, and ultimately ensure the integrity of research outcomes.

The case created with the help of Curre (University of Helsinki AI tool).

5.6. Summary

Importance of RE/RI training:

- Embed continuous, inclusive training that builds knowledge, skills, values, and habits for ethical self-regulation.
- Use pedagogy that promotes active, field-relevant, case-based learning to shape competencies.
- Prioritise supervision and safe learning environments for junior researchers and collaborators to navigate pressures and learn from mistakes.
- Relate ethical guidelines to societal consequences by teaching the impact of lost public trust and misuse of research misconduct narratives.

Role of RE/RI Training for Mentors and Supervisors:

- Provide ongoing, targeted training for senior researchers to lead by example in an effort to root ethical culture.
- Support and expect supervisors to model and encourage ethical norms through mentoring and team practices.

Pedagogy for RE/RI Training:

- Personalize learning with adaptive tools and discipline-sensitive content.
- Promote reflective practice to develop ethical reasoning and transfer to real contexts.
- Make collaborative discussion and group work core to foster deliberation and teamwork.
- Engage emotions through cases and role-play to connect awareness with moral reasoning.
- Use authentic ethical dilemmas and applications to bridge theory and practice.

- Train and support citizen scientists; ensure accessible, FAIR-aligned materials across formats and contexts.

Indicators of Effectiveness of RE/RI Training:

- Apply structured evaluation frameworks and taxonomies to identify depth of learning.
- Use learning analytics and authentic assessments responsibly to gauge engagement and decisions.
- Conduct transparent, longitudinal evaluations that promote reflection without penalizing learners.
- Establish continuous feedback loops to keep training adaptive and relevant.
- Combine quantitative and qualitative methods to capture changes in knowledge, behaviour, and values.
- Involve ethics education expertise in program design and assessment.
- Share evaluation outcomes to spread best practices and strengthen an RI culture.

5.7. Further Reading and Resources

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